

Egg Shape Analyses

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This R notebook summarises the code for all of the analyses in the ms ‘The Shapes of Birds’ Eggs: Evolutionary Constraints and Adaptations’ published in *The American Naturalist* (2021). The analyses here are

reported in the text, Tables and Figures of both the main text and the Supplementary Material. Additional analyses exploring data, assessing different model structures, and managing datasets are not included here but may be requested from the first author at mont@queensu.ca

This code assumes that the datasets are in a project folder that includes this notebook, otherwise you will have to set up a path to the data.

The relevant Figures and Tables are identified in the heading of each code chunk. Most figures were not made using R but rather by exporting the relevant data or analyses to DataGraph (v. 4.7).

1 July 2021
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1 R details and packages used

- File creation date: 2021-07-06
- R version 4.1.0 (2021-05-18)
- 'tidyverse' package version: 1.3.1
- 'sjPlot' package version: 2.8.8
- 'sjstats' package version: 0.18.1
- 'psych' package version: 2.1.6
- 'ggforce' package version: 0.3.3
- 'rptR' package version: 0.9.22
- 'smatr' package version: 3.4.8
- 'easystats' package version: 0.4.0
- 'geiger' package version: 2.0.7
- 'phytools' package version: 0.7.80
- 'phylolm' package version: 2.6.2
- 'DescTools' package version: 0.99.42

2 Load packages

```
library(tidyverse) #ggplot2, dplyr and the rest, all at once
library(sjPlot) #diagnostic and other data viz plots; gives a warning that you can ignore as we do not
library(sjstats) #lots of convenient functions
library(psych) #effect size, corr matrices
library(ggforce) #some convenience functions for ggplot
library(rptR) #repeatability analyses
library(smatr) #sma regression analyses for allometry
library(easystats) #some convenience functions
library(geiger) #phylogenetic analyses
library(phytools) #phylogenetic analyses
library(phylolm) #phylogenetic least squares analyses
library(DescTools) #descriptive stats
library(visreg) #functions for plotting regressions
```

3 GET THE DATA, PERFORM CONVERSIONS and PCAs

3.1 Main dataset, species averages; Figure 1b

```
dat1all <-read.csv("DATAeggshape.csv") #main species dataset for egg data
dat1 <- dat1all %>% mutate_if(is.character, as.factor)
# egg shape data plotted in Figure 11b
```

3.2 Conversions and scaling of variables, main dataset

```
dat1 <- dat1 %>% mutate(logLENGTH = log10(avLENGTH), logWIDTH = log10(avWIDTH), logPT = log10(avPT), log
#standardize variables
dat1$sVOL <- c(scale(log10(dat1$avVOL))) #scales, then c() changes matrix to numeric variable
dat1$sADmass <-c(scale(log10(dat1$ADmass)))
dat1$sRElegg <- c(scale(log10(dat1$RElegg)))
dat1$sHWI <- c(scale(dat1$HWI))
dat1$sCSegg <- c(scale(log10(dat1$CSegg)))
```

3.3 All birds: PCAs for female and egg size, egg shape, and pelvis dimensions

Tables S2, S3, and S4; Figures 1 and S3

```
correlation(dat1[, c("logADmass", "logVOL")])

## # Correlation Matrix (pearson-method)
##
## Parameter1 | Parameter2 |    r |      95% CI | t(942) |      p
## -----
## logADmass |    logVOL | 0.97 | [0.96, 0.97] | 115.77 | < .001***
##
## p-value adjustment method: Holm (1979)
## Observations: 944

##EGG SHAPE PCA
datPCA1<- dat1[, c("logPT", "logPA", "logEL")]
pairs(datPCA1)
```



```
correlation(datPCA1)
```

```
## # Correlation Matrix (pearson-method)
##
## Parameter1 | Parameter2 | r | 95% CI | t(953) | p
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
## logPT      | logPA      | 0.82 | [0.80, 0.84] | 44.46 | < .001***
## logPT      | logEL      | 0.35 | [0.30, 0.41] | 11.67 | < .001***
## logPA      | logEL      | 0.22 | [0.15, 0.28] | 6.82  | < .001***
##
## p-value adjustment method: Holm (1979)
## Observations: 955
```

```
#relationship between logPA and logPT is linear
```

```
glimpse(datPCA1)
```

```
## Rows: 955
## Columns: 3
## $ logPT <dbl> -0.2718956, -0.2719933, -0.2659369, -0.2845183, -0.2605202, -0.2~
## $ logPA <dbl> 0.13595800, 0.13162030, 0.08413498, 0.08740097, 0.15525131, 0.07~
## $ logEL <dbl> 0.10653571, 0.11435189, 0.10454804, 0.10338411, 0.11290615, 0.09~
```

```
cor.test.bartlett(datPCA1, n= 955, diag = TRUE)
```

```
## R was not square, finding R from data
## $chisq
## [1] 1215.374
##
## $p.value
## [1] 3.385342e-263
##
```

```
## $df
## [1] 3
```

```
##Bartlett test P<0.05 indicates that the reduction of dimensions is feasible
```

```
(modA1 <- principal(datPCA1, rotate = "varimax", nfactors = 2, scores = TRUE))
```

```
## Principal Components Analysis
## Call: principal(r = datPCA1, nfactors = 2, rotate = "varimax", scores = TRUE)
## Standardized loadings (pattern matrix) based upon correlation matrix
##      RC1  RC2  h2    u2 com
## logPT 0.92 0.24 0.91 0.0867 1.1
## logPA 0.96 0.07 0.92 0.0762 1.0
## logEL 0.14 0.99 1.00 0.0028 1.0
##
##
##      RC1  RC2
## SS loadings      1.79 1.04
## Proportion Var   0.60 0.35
## Cumulative Var   0.60 0.94
## Proportion Explained 0.63 0.37
## Cumulative Proportion 0.63 1.00
##
## Mean item complexity = 1.1
## Test of the hypothesis that 2 components are sufficient.
##
## The root mean square of the residuals (RMSR) is 0.05
## with the empirical chi square 13.5 with prob < NA
##
## Fit based upon off diagonal values = 0.99
```

```
summary(modA1) #Table S2
```

```
##
## Factor analysis with Call: principal(r = datPCA1, nfactors = 2, rotate = "varimax", scores = TRUE)
##
## Test of the hypothesis that 2 factors are sufficient.
## The degrees of freedom for the model is -2 and the objective function was 0.34
## The number of observations was 955 with Chi Square = 324.68 with prob < NA
##
## The root mean square of the residuals (RMSA) is 0.05
```

```
biplot(modA1)
```



```
pca1S <- as.data.frame(modA1$scores)
dat1 <- cbind(as.data.frame(dat1), pca1S[, 1:2])
dat1 <- dat1 %>% rename(RC1AS = RC1, RC2EL = RC2) #RC scores plotted in Figure 1c

##FEMALE and egg size PCA
datPCA2 <- dat1[, c("sVOL", "sADmass")]

pairs(datPCA2)
```



```
correlation(datPCA2)
```

```
## # Correlation Matrix (pearson-method)
##
## Parameter1 | Parameter2 | r | 95% CI | t(942) | p
## -----
## sVOL      | sADmass | 0.97 | [0.96, 0.97] | 115.77 | < .001***
##
## p-value adjustment method: Holm (1979)
## Observations: 944
```

```
##relationship is linear
```

```
modA2 <- principal(datPCA2, rotate = "none", nfactors = 2, scores = TRUE)
summary(modA2) #Table S3
```

```
##
## Factor analysis with Call: principal(r = datPCA2, nfactors = 2, rotate = "none", scores = TRUE)
##
## Test of the hypothesis that 2 factors are sufficient.
## The degrees of freedom for the model is -2 and the objective function was 0
## The number of observations was 955 with Chi Square = 0 with prob < NA
##
## The root mean square of the residuals (RMSA) is 0
```

```
modA2
```

```
## Principal Components Analysis
## Call: principal(r = datPCA2, nfactors = 2, rotate = "none", scores = TRUE)
## Standardized loadings (pattern matrix) based upon correlation matrix
##      PC1  PC2 h2 u2 com
## sVOL  0.99 -0.13 1 0 1
## sADmass 0.99  0.13 1 0 1
##
```

```
##          PC1  PC2
## SS loadings      1.97 0.03
## Proportion Var    0.98 0.02
## Cumulative Var    0.98 1.00
## Proportion Explained 0.98 0.02
## Cumulative Proportion 0.98 1.00
##
## Mean item complexity = 1
## Test of the hypothesis that 2 components are sufficient.
##
## The root mean square of the residuals (RMSR) is 0
## with the empirical chi square 0 with prob < NA
##
## Fit based upon off diagonal values = 1
```

```
biplot(modA2)
```



```
pca2S <- as.data.frame(modA2$scores)
dat1 <- cbind(as.data.frame(dat1), pca2S[, 1:2])
dat1 <- dat1 %>% rename(PC1mass = PC1, PC2relegg = PC2)
dat1 <- dat1 %>% mutate(PC2relegg = -PC2relegg)

#corr between PC2relegg and residuals from Vol on Mass
dat1naMass <- dat1 %>% drop_na(logADmass)
modA1 <- lm(logVOL ~ logADmass, data = dat1naMass)
summary(modA1)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = logVOL ~ logADmass, data = dat1naMass)
```

```
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -0.54151 -0.11265 -0.02965  0.09094  0.62620
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.668065   0.016090  -41.52  <2e-16 ***
## logADmass   0.800988   0.006919  115.77  <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 0.1759 on 942 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.9343, Adjusted R-squared:  0.9343
## F-statistic: 1.34e+04 on 1 and 942 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

```
dat1naMass$res <- residuals(modA1)
```

```
correlation(dat1naMass[, c("res", "PC2relegg", "logADmass", "logVOL") ])
```

```
## # Correlation Matrix (pearson-method)
```

```
##
## Parameter1 | Parameter2 |      r |      95% CI | t(942) |      p
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
## res      | PC2relegg |  0.99 | [ 0.99,  0.99] | 228.22 | < .001***
## res      | logADmass | 8.98e-17 | [-0.06,  0.06] | 2.76e-15 | > .999
## res      | logVOL    |  0.26 | [ 0.20,  0.31] |  8.14 | < .001***
## PC2relegg | logADmass | -0.13 | [-0.20, -0.07] | -4.13 | < .001***
## PC2relegg | logVOL    |  0.13 | [ 0.06,  0.19] |  3.87 | < .001***
## logADmass | logVOL    |  0.97 | [ 0.96,  0.97] | 115.77 | < .001***
##
```

```
## p-value adjustment method: Holm (1979)
```

```
## Observations: 944
```

```
ggplot(dat1naMass, aes(x = res, y = PC2relegg)) +
  theme_bw() +
  geom_point(color="coral", size=2) +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, linetype="solid",
             color="black", size=1, na.rm = TRUE) +
  theme(legend.position = "none") #Figure S3
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```



```
#other correlations
correlation(dat1[, c("PC1mass", "PC2relegg", "sVOL", "sADmass", "RC1AS", "RC2EL")])
```

```
## # Correlation Matrix (pearson-method)
##
## Parameter1 | Parameter2 | r | 95% CI | t | df | p
## -----
## PC1mass | PC2relegg | -4.18e-03 | [-0.07, 0.06] | -0.13 | 942 | > .999
## PC1mass | sVOL | 0.99 | [ 0.99, 0.99] | 235.41 | 942 | < .001***
## PC1mass | sADmass | 0.99 | [ 0.99, 0.99] | 235.67 | 942 | < .001***
## PC1mass | RC1AS | -0.09 | [-0.15, -0.03] | -2.78 | 942 | 0.028*
## PC1mass | RC2EL | 0.24 | [ 0.18, 0.30] | 7.61 | 942 | < .001***
## PC2relegg | sVOL | 0.13 | [ 0.06, 0.19] | 3.87 | 942 | < .001***
## PC2relegg | sADmass | -0.13 | [-0.20, -0.07] | -4.13 | 942 | < .001***
## PC2relegg | RC1AS | 0.12 | [ 0.05, 0.18] | 3.64 | 942 | 0.002**
## PC2relegg | RC2EL | 0.06 | [ 0.00, 0.13] | 1.96 | 942 | 0.152
## sVOL | sADmass | 0.97 | [ 0.96, 0.97] | 115.77 | 942 | < .001***
## sVOL | RC1AS | -0.08 | [-0.14, -0.02] | -2.43 | 953 | 0.061
## sVOL | RC2EL | 0.25 | [ 0.19, 0.30] | 7.83 | 953 | < .001***
## sADmass | RC1AS | -0.10 | [-0.17, -0.04] | -3.23 | 942 | 0.008**
## sADmass | RC2EL | 0.23 | [ 0.17, 0.29] | 7.26 | 942 | < .001***
## RC1AS | RC2EL | -3.08e-17 | [-0.06, 0.06] | -9.50e-16 | 953 | > .999
##
## p-value adjustment method: Holm (1979)
## Observations: 944-955
```

```
###PELVIS dimensions PCA
#for Table S4
```

```

##Shatkovska data
dat2 <- read.csv("DATApelvis.csv")
dat2 <- dat2 %>% mutate_if(is.character, as.factor)
dat2 <- dat2 %>% drop_na(avLS)
rownames(dat2) <- dat2[,5]
dat2[,5] <- NULL

dat2$sHWI = as.numeric(scale(dat2$HWI))

datPCA3<- dat2[, c("avLS", "avWacet", "avWish", "avLRpostpre", "avLRilanti")]
pairs(datPCA3)

```



```

datPCA3.1 <- log10(datPCA3) #log-transform to normalize
pairs(datPCA3.1)

```



```
correlation(datPCA3.1)
```

```
## # Correlation Matrix (pearson-method)
##
## Parameter1 | Parameter2 | r | 95% CI | t(171) | p
## -----
## avLS | avWacet | 0.88 | [ 0.84, 0.91] | 23.71 | < .001***
## avLS | avWish | 0.85 | [ 0.80, 0.89] | 20.99 | < .001***
## avLS | avLRpostpre | 0.03 | [-0.12, 0.18] | 0.39 | 0.699
## avLS | avLRilanti | 0.68 | [ 0.59, 0.76] | 12.23 | < .001***
## avWacet | avWish | 0.89 | [ 0.85, 0.92] | 25.47 | < .001***
## avWacet | avLRpostpre | -0.19 | [-0.33, -0.04] | -2.50 | 0.040*
## avWacet | avLRilanti | 0.28 | [ 0.13, 0.41] | 3.79 | < .001***
## avWish | avLRpostpre | 0.08 | [-0.07, 0.23] | 1.09 | 0.556
## avWish | avLRilanti | 0.38 | [ 0.24, 0.50] | 5.31 | < .001***
## avLRpostpre | avLRilanti | 0.28 | [ 0.14, 0.41] | 3.84 | < .001***
##
## p-value adjustment method: Holm (1979)
## Observations: 173
```

```
glimpse(datPCA3.1)
```

```
## Rows: 173
## Columns: 5
## $ avLS <dbl> 1.779236, 1.527630, 2.105851, 1.983175, 1.962843, 1.923244~
## $ avWacet <dbl> 1.551450, 1.322219, 1.740363, 1.641474, 1.582063, 1.453318~
## $ avWish <dbl> 1.586024, 1.338456, 1.740363, 1.673942, 1.653213, 1.612784~
## $ avLRpostpre <dbl> -0.20065945, -0.37675071, -0.18045606, -0.35654732, -0.327~
## $ avLRilanti <dbl> 0.16136800, 0.19312460, 0.30963017, 0.28555731, 0.28780173~
```

```
cortest.bartlett(datPCA3.1, n= 173, diag = TRUE)
```

```
## R was not square, finding R from data
```

```
## $chisq  
## [1] 1015.535
```

```
##  
## $p.value  
## [1] 8.420574e-212
```

```
##  
## $df  
## [1] 10
```

```
##Bartlett test P<0.05 indicates that the reduction of dimensions is feasible
```

```
(modA3 <- principal(datPCA3.1, rotate = "varimax", nfactors = 2, scores = TRUE))
```

```
## Principal Components Analysis
```

```
## Call: principal(r = datPCA3.1, nfactors = 2, rotate = "varimax", scores = TRUE)
```

```
## Standardized loadings (pattern matrix) based upon correlation matrix
```

```
##          RC1  RC2  h2   u2 com  
## avLS      0.96  0.22  0.97  0.031  1.1  
## avWacet   0.96 -0.16  0.95  0.052  1.1  
## avWish    0.92  0.10  0.86  0.140  1.0  
## avLRpostpre -0.13  0.89  0.81  0.193  1.0  
## avLRilanti  0.50  0.67  0.70  0.305  1.9
```

```
##  
##          RC1  RC2  
## SS loadings      2.96  1.32  
## Proportion Var   0.59  0.26  
## Cumulative Var   0.59  0.86  
## Proportion Explained 0.69  0.31  
## Cumulative Proportion 0.69  1.00
```

```
##  
## Mean item complexity = 1.2  
## Test of the hypothesis that 2 components are sufficient.  
##  
## The root mean square of the residuals (RMSR) is 0.11  
## with the empirical chi square 41.69 with prob < 1.1e-10  
##  
## Fit based upon off diagonal values = 0.96
```

```
summary(datPCA3.1) #Table S4
```

```
##          avLS          avWacet          avWish          avLRpostpre  
## Min.      :0.9494    Min.      :0.8096    Min.      :0.8921    Min.      :-0.49485  
## 1st Qu.:1.3263    1st Qu.:1.1173    1st Qu.:1.2788    1st Qu.: -0.18046  
## Median :1.6232    Median :1.2833    Median :1.4409    Median :-0.04576  
## Mean      :1.5716    Mean      :1.2842    Mean      :1.4354    Mean      :-0.07085  
## 3rd Qu.:1.8126    3rd Qu.:1.4800    3rd Qu.:1.5977    3rd Qu.: 0.03342  
## Max.      :2.5478    Max.      :1.8457    Max.      :1.9096    Max.      : 0.42813  
##          avLRilanti  
## Min.      :0.004321  
## 1st Qu.:0.148191  
## Median :0.220108  
## Mean      :0.249898  
## 3rd Qu.:0.326336  
## Max.      :0.859739
```

```
biplot(modA3)
```



```
nobs(modA3)
```

```
## [1] 173
```

```
pca3S <- modA3$scores  
dat2 <- cbind(dat2, pca3S[, 1:2])  
dat2 <- dat2 %>% rename(RC1meas = RC1, RC2ratios = RC2)
```

3.4 Neoves (neognaths) data frame

Reduce main dataset to just the neoaves (delete Paleognaths)

```
paleo <- c("Struthioniformes", "Casuariiformes", "Rheiformes", "Apterygiformes", "Tinamiformes")  
datineo <- dat1 %>% filter(!Order %in% paleo) #remove species of paleognaths  
datineoNA <- datineo %>% drop_na(PC1mass) #remove species with no data for female mass
```

4 OVIDUCT ANALYSES

These analyses are on data for 28 species of Galliformes. Calculated allometric slopes of model II regressions for length and mass for the full oviduct and the lengths of different sections. ## Get oviduct data for Galliformes; perform conversions

```
dat3 <- read.csv("DATAoviducts.csv") #mean egg and oviduct data for each species  
  
##calculate diameters of lumens of different sections of the oviduct  
##from mean values for each species assuming the lumen is fully stretched  
dat3$MAGLUMENDiam = dat3$MAGLUMENperim/pi
```

```

dat3$ISTHLUMENDiam = dat3$ISTHLUMENperim/pi
dat3$UTERUSLUMENDiam = dat3$UTERUSLUMENperim/pi
dat3$VAGLUMENDiam = dat3$VAGLUMENperim/pi

dat3 <- dat3 %>% mutate(logVOL = log10(VOL))
dat3 <- dat3 %>% mutate(logADmass = log10(ADmassOVI))
dat3 <- dat3 %>% mutate(logISTHdiam = log10(ISTHLUMENDiam))
dat3 <- dat3 %>% mutate(logISTHlen = log10(ISTHMUSlength))

#dataset without species with NA for key variables
dat3NA <- dat3 %>% drop_na()

```

4.1 Repeatability analysis

Repeatability of oviduct length for SM section ‘Oviducts in the Galliformes’

```

dat4 <- read.csv("DATAovilengths.csv") #three measures of ovi length for each oviduct

rpt(oviductlength ~ (1|birdID), grname = "birdID", data = dat4)

```

```

## Warning in if (datatype == "Gaussian") {: the condition has length > 1 and only
## the first element will be used

```

```

## Warning in rptGaussian(formula, grname, data, CI, nboot, npermut, parallel, : 7
## rows containing missing values were removed

```

```

## Bootstrap Progress:

```

```

##
##
## Repeatability estimation using the lmm method
##
## Repeatability for birdID
## R = 0.997
## SE = 0.001
## CI = [0.996, 0.998]
## P = 6.6e-163 [LRT]
## NA [Permutation]

```

```

(nbirds <- dat4 %>% group_by(birdID) %>% summarise(number = n()))

```

```

## # A tibble: 72 x 2
##   birdID number
##   <chr>   <int>
## 1 BF01     3
## 2 BF02     3
## 3 BP01     3
## 4 BP02     3
## 5 BP03     3
## 6 BQ01     3
## 7 BQ02     3
## 8 C01      3
## 9 C02      3
## 10 CAQ01   3
## # ... with 62 more rows

```

4.2 Oviduct length allometries

Table S10; Figure 3a

```
##SMA regressions
(modB1 <- sma(OVImass ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))

## Call: sma(formula = OVImass ~ ADmassOVI, data = dat3, log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate   -1.039733  0.7978451
## lower limit -1.290590  0.7127392
## upper limit -0.788876  0.8931133
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.921372
## P-value : 7.0672e-16
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.6305 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 0.00032274

plot(modB1, xlab = "log10 Adult mass", ylab = "log10 Oviduct mass", cex = 2, pch = 18, col = "coral")
```



```
(modB2<- sma(OVIlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))
```

```
## Call: sma(formula = OVIlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = dat3, log = "xy",
##   slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    1.905630 0.2806220
## lower limit  1.786538 0.2410624
## upper limit  2.024722 0.3266736
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.8568196
## P-value : 1.7691e-12
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9744 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : < 2.22e-16
```

```
plot(modB2, xlab = "log10 Adult mass", ylab = "log10 Oviduct length", cex = 2, pch = 18, col = "coral")
```



```
(modB3 <- sma(INFUNDlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))
```

```
## Call: sma(formula = INFUNDlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = dat3, log = "xy",
##   slope.test = 1)
```

```

##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    0.7913808 0.3659926
## lower limit 0.5007093 0.2762628
## upper limit 1.0820523 0.4848666
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.5002352
## P-value : 2.5719e-05
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.8584 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 5.1582e-09

```

```
(modB4 <- sma(MAGNUMlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))
```

```

## Call: sma(formula = MAGNUMlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = dat3, log = "xy",
##           slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    1.470912 0.2923339
## lower limit 1.315752 0.2418504
## upper limit 1.626072 0.3533551
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.7761825
## P-value : 6.1595e-10
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9572 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 1.5543e-15

```

```
(modB5 <- sma(ISTHMUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))
```

```

## Call: sma(formula = ISTHMUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = dat3, log = "xy",
##           slope.test = 1)
##

```

```

## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate   1.0766004 0.3027611
## lower limit 0.9003198 0.2459842
## upper limit 1.2528810 0.3726429
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.7307623
## P-value : 6.9921e-09
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9451 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 3.8636e-14
(modB6 <- sma(UTERUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))

```

```

## Call: sma(formula = UTERUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = dat3, log = "xy",
##           slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate   1.0442379 0.2895309
## lower limit 0.8448668 0.2266609
## upper limit 1.2436091 0.3698395
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.6237888
## P-value : 5.8136e-07
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9324 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 5.3446e-13

```

```

(modB7 <- sma(VAGINALlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))

```

```

## Call: sma(formula = VAGINALlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = dat3, log = "xy",
##           slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis

```

```

##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    0.8428138 0.3688959
## lower limit 0.6394324 0.3029899
## upper limit 1.0461952 0.4491378
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.758541
## P-value : 1.6689e-09
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9221 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 3.1769e-12

```

```

(modB8 <- sma(OVIlenght ~ OVImass, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3))

```

```

## Call: sma(formula = OVIlenght ~ OVImass, data = dat3, log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    2.271330 0.3517249
## lower limit 2.218182 0.3103704
## upper limit 2.324478 0.3985896
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.9032199
## P-value : 1.0616e-14
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9702 with 26 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : < 2.22e-16

```

```

modB9 <- sma(ISTHLUMENDiam ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, data = dat3)
plot(modB9, xlab = "Adult mass", ylab = "Isthmus lumen diameter", cex = 2, pch = 18, col = "coral")

```



```
plot(modB9, which="qq")
```



```
#allometries with adult mass: just the Phasianidae
(modB10 <- sma(OVImass ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianidae")))
```

```
## Call: sma(formula = OVImass ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3, Family ==
## "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
```

```
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate  -0.9759653  0.7765370
## lower limit -1.2604454  0.6819871
## upper limit -0.6914851  0.8841950
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.9132898
## P-value : 3.6522e-13
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.6555 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 0.00050652
```

```
plot(modB10, xlab = "log10 Adult mass", ylab = "log10 Oviduct mass", cex = 2, pch = 18, col = "coral")
```



```
(modB11<- sma(OVIlengh ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianidae"))
```

```
## Call: sma(formula = OVIlengh ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3, Family ==
## "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
```

```
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    1.911748 0.2793858
## lower limit  1.771725 0.2340299
## upper limit  2.051772 0.3335319
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.8377991
## P-value : 3.7271e-10
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9715 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 3.1086e-15
```

```
plot(modB11, xlab = "log10 Adult mass", ylab = "log10 Oviduct length", cex = 2, pch = 18, col = "coral")
```



```
(modB12 <- sma(INFUNDlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianidae"))
```

```
## Call: sma(formula = INFUNDlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3, Family ==
## "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
```

```

## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate  0.7665092 0.3747382
## lower limit 0.4262409 0.2730063
## upper limit 1.1067774 0.5143791
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.4694589
## P-value : 0.00022045
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.8441 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 2.1674e-07
(modB13 <- sma(MAGNUMlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianid
## Call: sma(formula = MAGNUMlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3, Family ==
##           "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate  1.535764 0.2727172
## lower limit 1.374884 0.2214930
## upper limit 1.696643 0.3357880
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.7753908
## P-value : 1.3856e-08
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9631 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 4.9516e-14
(modB14 <- sma(ISTHMUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasiani
## Call: sma(formula = ISTHMUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3,
##           Family == "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:

```

```

##           elevation      slope
## estimate    1.0698291 0.3050707
## lower limit 0.8610982 0.2398246
## upper limit 1.2785600 0.3880675
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.698043
## P-value : 3.7646e-07
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.938 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 1.3534e-11
(modB15 <- sma(UTERUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianid
## Call: sma(formula = UTERUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3, Family ==
## "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    1.0036214 0.2999975
## lower limit 0.7790698 0.2306906
## upper limit 1.2281730 0.3901264
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.638811
## P-value : 2.8084e-06
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9297 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 5.1681e-11
(modB16 <- sma(VAGINALength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianid
## Call: sma(formula = VAGINALength ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3, Family ==
## "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope

```

```

## estimate      0.8282091 0.3721691
## lower limit  0.5913041 0.2974212
## upper limit  1.0651142 0.4657027
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.7385488
## P-value : 7.5283e-08
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9147 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 4.0181e-10
(modB17 <- sma(OVIlength ~ OVI mass, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianidae"))

## Call: sma(formula = OVIlength ~ OVI mass, data = subset(dat3, Family ==
## "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##          elevation      slope
## estimate    2.262885 0.3597843
## lower limit  2.198085 0.3109941
## upper limit  2.327686 0.4162290
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.8905959
## P-value : 4.7657e-12
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9646 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 3.1974e-14
(modB18 <- sma(ISTHLUMENDiam ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianidae"))

## Call: sma(formula = ISTHLUMENDiam ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3,
## Family == "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##          elevation      slope
## estimate    0.3872409 0.3755559

```

```
## lower limit 0.1795324 0.3089465
## upper limit 0.5949494 0.4565264
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.8025288
## P-value : 3.3094e-09
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.9321 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 3.5521e-11
```

```
plot(modB18, xlab = "Adult mass", ylab = "Isthmus lumen diameter", cex = 2, pch = 18, col = "coral") #Figure
```



```
plot(modB18, which = "qq")
```



```
(modB19 <- sma(ISTHMUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, log = "xy", slope.test = 1, subset(dat3, Family == "Phasianidae")))
```

```
## Call: sma(formula = ISTHMUSlength ~ ADmassOVI, data = subset(dat3,
##   Family == "Phasianidae"), log = "xy", slope.test = 1)
##
## Fit using Standardized Major Axis
##
## These variables were log-transformed before fitting: xy
##
## Confidence intervals (CI) are at 95%
##
## -----
## Coefficients:
##           elevation      slope
## estimate    1.0698291 0.3050707
## lower limit 0.8610982 0.2398246
## upper limit 1.2785600 0.3880675
##
## H0 : variables uncorrelated
## R-squared : 0.698043
## P-value : 3.7646e-07
##
## -----
## H0 : slope not different from 1
## Test statistic : r= -0.938 with 22 degrees of freedom under H0
## P-value : 1.3534e-11
```

```
plot(modB19, xlab = "Adult mass", ylab = "Isthmus length", cex =2, pch = 18,col="coral")
```



```
plot(modB19, which="qq")
```


5 AVIAN FAMILIES: medium to large Families

Models with single predictors; all loops have the same structure in this and the next code chunk so annotation in the first loop applies to all of them *## Elongation Table S9a; Figure 2c-f*

```
options(na.action = na.omit)
Nfams <- nlevels(dat1neoNA$Family) #number of families in dataset
fams <- levels(dat1neoNA$Family) #name of each family

###ELONGATION
####only PC1mass as predictor
#initialize variables
numx = 0
FEM = 0
FEMlow = FEMup = 0
MNrelegg = 0
r2 = 0
obs = 0
ct = ffam = 0

#PC1mass as predictor
for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i]) #dataset for ith family
  numx <- nrow(datx) #number of rows in dataset for this family
  if (numx >4 ) { #if fewer than 4 species in the family then skip it
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat10 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i]) #specify the dataset to use
    modC1 <- lm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass, data = dat10) #LM to predict elongation from adult mass
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
    #print(summary(modC1))
    CONF <- confint(modC1) #calculate 95%CL for model parameters
    FEM[ct] = modC1$coefficients[2] #put model coefficients in a matrix
    FEMlow[ct] = CONF[2,1] #put lower 95%CL for slope into a variable
    FEMup[ct] = CONF[2,2] #put upper 95%CL for slope into a variable
    rsq <- r2(modC1) #calculate model R2
    r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1] #put R2 into a variable
    obs[ct] <- nobs(modC1) #put no. of species into a variable
  } else {
    cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
  }
}
}
```

```
## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
```

no, Balaenicipitidae
no, Bombycillidae
no, Bucconidae
no, Bucerotidae
no, Buphagidae
no, Burhinidae
no, Cacatuidae
no, Calcariidae
no, Callaeidae
no, Calyptomenidae
no, Cardinalidae
no, Cariamidae
no, Casuariidae
no, Cathartidae
no, Certhiidae
no, Cettiidae
no, Chionidae
no, Chloropseidae
no, Ciconiidae
no, Cinclidae
no, Cinclosomatidae
no, Climacteridae
no, Coliidae
no, Conopophagidae
no, Coraciidae
no, Corcoracidae
no, Cotingidae
no, Dasyornithidae
no, Dicaeidae
no, Dicruridae
no, Donacobiidae
no, Dromadidae
no, Estrildidae
no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae

no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae
no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreoicidae
no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae
no, Pelecanidae
no, Pellorneidae
no, Phaethontidae
no, Philepittidae
no, Phoenicopteridae
no, Phoeniculidae
no, Phylloscopidae
no, Picathartidae
no, Pipridae
no, Pittidae
no, Pluvianidae
no, Podargidae
no, Podicipedidae
no, Polioptilidae
no, Promeropidae
no, Prunellidae
no, Psittacidae
no, Psophiidae
no, Ptiliogonatidae
no, Ptilonorhynchidae
no, Ramphastidae
no, Recurvirostridae
no, Regulidae
no, Remizidae
no, Rheidae
no, Rhinocryptidae
no, Rhipiduridae
no, Rhynochetidae
no, Rostratulidae
no, Sagittariidae
no, Sarothruridae
no, Scopidae
no, Sittidae
no, Steatornithidae

```
## no, Stercorariidae
## no, Strigopidae
## no, Struthionidae
## no, Thamnophilidae
## no, Thinocoridae
## no, Thraupidae
## no, Tichodromidae
## no, Timaliidae
## no, Tinamidae
## no, Todidae
## no, Trogonidae
## no, Turnicidae
## no, Tytonidae
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(FEM, fill = "coral", bins = 20) #plot distribution of model coefficients
```



```
comboC1 <- data.frame(ffam, FEM, FEMlow, FEMup, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for each fami
colnames(comboC1) <- c("Family", "FEMmass", "FEMlow", "FEMup", "Rsq", "Nspecies") #label the columns

write.csv(comboC1, "famCOEFFSfemEL.csv") #save data to compile Table S9a

####only PC2relegg as predictor
numx = 0
EGG = FEM = CS = HWI = 0
```

```

FEMlow = FEMup =EGGlow =EGGup =CSlow =CSup =HWIlow =HWIup = 0
MNrelegg = 0
r2 = 0
obs = 0
ct = ffam = 0

for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
  numx <- nrow(datx)
  if (numx >4 ) {
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat11 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
    modC2 <- lm(RC2EL ~ PC2relegg, data = dat11)
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
    #print(summary(modC2))
    CONF <- confint(modC2)
    EGG[ct] = modC2$coefficients[2]
    EGGlow[ct] = CONF[2,1]
    EGGup[ct] =CONF[2,2]
    MNrelegg[ct] <- mean(dat11$PC2relegg, na.rm = TRUE)
    rsq <- r2(modC2)
    r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1]
    obs[ct] <- nobs(modC2)
  } else {
    cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
  }
}
}

```

```

## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
## no, Balaenicipitidae
## no, Bombycillidae
## no, Bucconidae
## no, Bucerotidae
## no, Buphagidae
## no, Burhinidae
## no, Cacatuidae
## no, Calcariidae
## no, Callaeidae
## no, Calyptomenidae
## no, Cardinalidae
## no, Cariamidae
## no, Casuariidae

```

no, Cathartidae
no, Certhiidae
no, Cettiidae
no, Chionidae
no, Chloropseidae
no, Ciconiidae
no, Cinclidae
no, Cinclosomatidae
no, Climacteridae
no, Coliidae
no, Conopophagidae
no, Coraciidae
no, Corcoracidae
no, Cotingidae
no, Dasyornithidae
no, Dicaeidae
no, Dicruridae
no, Donacobiidae
no, Dromadidae
no, Estrildidae
no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae
no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae
no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreoicidae

no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae
no, Pelecanidae
no, Pellorneidae
no, Phaethontidae
no, Philepittidae
no, Phoenicopteridae
no, Phoeniculidae
no, Phylloscopidae
no, Picathartidae
no, Pipridae
no, Pittidae
no, Pluvianidae
no, Podargidae
no, Podicipedidae
no, Polioptilidae
no, Promeropidae
no, Prunellidae
no, Psittacidae
no, Psophiidae
no, Ptiliogonatidae
no, Ptilonorhynchidae
no, Ramphastidae
no, Recurvirostridae
no, Regulidae
no, Remizidae
no, Rheidae
no, Rhinocryptidae
no, Rhipiduridae
no, Rhynochetidae
no, Rostratulidae
no, Sagittariidae
no, Sarothruridae
no, Scopidae
no, Sittidae
no, Steatornithidae
no, Stercorariidae
no, Strigopidae
no, Struthionidae
no, Thamnophilidae
no, Thinocoridae
no, Thraupidae
no, Tichodromidae
no, Timaliidae
no, Tinamidae
no, Todidae
no, Trogonidae
no, Turnicidae
no, Tytonidae

```
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(EGG, fill = "coral", bins = 20)
```



```
comboC2 <- data.frame(ffam, EGG,EGGlow,EGGup, MNrelegg, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for
colnames(comboC2) <- c("Family", "EGG","EGGlow","EGGup","MEANrelegg","Rsq","Nspecies")

write.csv(comboC2, "famCOEFFSrelegg1EL.csv") #Table S9a

modC2LM <- lm(EGG ~ MEANrelegg, data = comboC2)
summary(modC2LM)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = EGG ~ MEANrelegg, data = comboC2)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.9445 -0.1753  0.0723  0.3223  1.9111
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.15771    0.09685  -1.628   0.109
## MEANrelegg   0.17846    0.12457   1.433   0.158
##
```

```
## Residual standard error: 0.7195 on 54 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared: 0.03661, Adjusted R-squared: 0.01877
## F-statistic: 2.052 on 1 and 54 DF, p-value: 0.1578
```

```
###only clutch size as predictor
numx = 0
EGG = FEM = CS = HWI = 0
FEMlow = FEMup =EGGlow =EGGup =CSlow =CSup =HWIlow =HWIup = 0
MNrelegg = 0
r2 = 0
obs = 0
ct = ffam = 0

for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
  numx <- nrow(datx)
  if (numx >4 ) {
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat12 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
    modC3 <- lm(RC2EL ~ sCSeg, data = dat12)
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
    #print(summary(modC3))
    CONF <- confint(modC3)
    CS[ct] = modC3$coefficients[2]
    CSlow[ct] = CONF[2,1]
    CSup[ct] = CONF[2,2]
    rsq <- r2(modC3)
    r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1]
    obs[ct] <- nobs(modC3)
  } else {
    cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
  }
}
}
```

```
## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
## no, Balaenicipitidae
## no, Bombycillidae
## no, Bucconidae
## no, Bucerotidae
## no, Buphagidae
## no, Burhinidae
## no, Cacatuidae
## no, Calcariidae
```

no, Callaeidae
no, Calyptomenidae
no, Cardinalidae
no, Cariamidae
no, Casuariidae
no, Cathartidae
no, Certhiidae
no, Cettiidae
no, Chionidae
no, Chloropseidae
no, Ciconiidae
no, Cinclidae
no, Cinclosomatidae
no, Climacteridae
no, Coliidae
no, Conopophagidae
no, Coraciidae
no, Corcoracidae
no, Cotingidae
no, Dasyornithidae
no, Dicaeidae
no, Dicruridae
no, Donacobiidae
no, Dromadidae
no, Estrildidae
no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae
no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae

no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreoicidae
no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae
no, Pelecanidae
no, Pellorneidae
no, Phaethontidae
no, Philepittidae
no, Phoenicopteridae
no, Phoeniculidae
no, Phylloscopidae
no, Picathartidae
no, Pipridae
no, Pittidae
no, Pluvianidae
no, Podargidae
no, Podicipedidae
no, Polioptilidae
no, Promeropidae
no, Prunellidae
no, Psittacidae
no, Psophiidae
no, Ptiliogonatidae
no, Ptilonorhynchidae
no, Ramphastidae
no, Recurvirostridae
no, Regulidae
no, Remizidae
no, Rheidae
no, Rhinocryptidae
no, Rhipiduridae
no, Rhynochetidae
no, Rostratulidae
no, Sagittariidae
no, Sarothruridae
no, Scopidae
no, Sittidae
no, Steatornithidae
no, Stercorariidae
no, Strigopidae
no, Struthionidae
no, Thamnophilidae
no, Thinocoridae
no, Thraupidae
no, Tichodromidae
no, Timaliidae

```
## no, Tinamidae
## no, Todidae
## no, Trogonidae
## no, Turnicidae
## no, Tytonidae
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(CS, fill = "coral", bins = 20)
```

```
## Warning: Removed 4 rows containing non-finite values (stat_bin).
```



```
comboC3 <- data.frame(ffam, CS,CSlow,CSup, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for each family
colnames(comboC3) <- c("Family","CS","CSlow","CSup", "Rsq","Nspecies")
```

```
write.csv(comboC3, "famCOEFFScsEL.csv") #Table S9a
```

```
#####only HWI as predictor
```

```
numx = 0
```

```
EGG = FEM = CS = HWI = 0
```

```
FEMlow = FEMup =EGGlow =EGGup =CSlow =CSup =HWIlow =HWIup = 0
```

```
MNrelegg = 0
```

```
r2 = 0
```

```
obs = 0
```

```
ct = ffam = 0
```

```

for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
  numx <- nrow(datx)
  if (numx >4 ) {
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat13 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
    modC4 <- lm(RC2EL ~ SHWI, data = dat13)
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
    #print(summary(modC4))
    CONF <- confint(modC4)
    HWI[ct] = modC4$coefficients[2]
    HWIlow[ct] = CONF[2,1]
    HWIup[ct] = CONF[2,2]
    rsq <- r2(modC4)
    r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1]
    obs[ct] <- nobs(modC4)
  } else {
    cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
  }
}
}

```

```

## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
## no, Balaenicipitidae
## no, Bombycillidae
## no, Bucconidae
## no, Bucerotidae
## no, Buphagidae
## no, Burhinidae
## no, Cacatuidae
## no, Calcariidae
## no, Callaeidae
## no, Calyptomenidae
## no, Cardinalidae
## no, Cariamidae
## no, Casuariidae
## no, Cathartidae
## no, Certhiidae
## no, Cettiidae
## no, Chionidae
## no, Chloropseidae
## no, Ciconiidae
## no, Cinclidae

```

no, Cinclosomatidae
no, Climacteridae
no, Coliidae
no, Conopophagidae
no, Coraciidae
no, Corcoracidae
no, Cotingidae
no, Dasyornithidae
no, Dicaeidae
no, Dicruridae
no, Donacobiidae
no, Dromadidae
no, Estrildidae
no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae
no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae
no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreocidae
no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae

```
## no, Pelecanidae
## no, Pellorneidae
## no, Phaethontidae
## no, Philepittidae
## no, Phoenicopteridae
## no, Phoeniculidae
## no, Phylloscopidae
## no, Picathartidae
## no, Pipridae
## no, Pittidae
## no, Pluvianidae
## no, Podargidae
## no, Podicipedidae
## no, Polioptilidae
## no, Promeropidae
## no, Prunellidae
## no, Psittacidae
## no, Psophiidae
## no, Ptiliogonatidae
## no, Ptilonorhynchidae
## no, Ramphastidae
## no, Recurvirostridae
## no, Regulidae
## no, Remizidae
## no, Rheidae
## no, Rhinocryptidae
## no, Rhipiduridae
## no, Rhynochetidae
## no, Rostratulidae
## no, Sagittariidae
## no, Sarothruridae
## no, Scopidae
## no, Sittidae
## no, Steatornithidae
## no, Stercorariidae
## no, Strigopidae
## no, Struthionidae
## no, Thamnophilidae
## no, Thinocoridae
## no, Thraupidae
## no, Tichodromidae
## no, Timaliidae
## no, Tinamidae
## no, Todidae
## no, Trogonidae
## no, Turnicidae
## no, Tytonidae
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(HWI, fill = "coral", bins = 20)
```



```

comboC4 <- data.frame(ffam, HWI,HWIlow, HWIup, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for each fam
colnames(comboC4) <- c("Family", "HWI", "HWIlow", "HWIup", "Rsq", "Nspecies")

write.csv(comboC4, "famCOEFFShwiEL.csv") #Table S9a

```

5.1 Asymmetry

Table S9b; Figure 2g-j

```

#####only PC1mass as predictor
numx = 0
EGG = FEM = CS = HWI = 0
FEMlow = FEMup =EGGlow =EGGup =CSlow =CSup =HWIlow =HWIup = 0
MNrelegg = 0
r2 = 0
obs = 0
ct = ffam = 0

for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
  numx <- nrow(datx)
  if (numx >4 ) {
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat14 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
    modC5 <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass, data = dat14)
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
  }
}

```

```

#print(summary(modC5))
CONF <- confint(modC5)
FEM[ct] = modC5$coefficients[2]
FEMlow[ct] = CONF[2,1]
FEMup[ct] = CONF[2,2]
rsq <- r2(modC5)
r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1]
obs[ct] <- nobs(modC5)
} else {
  cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
}
}
}

```

```

## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
## no, Balaenicipitidae
## no, Bombycillidae
## no, Bucconidae
## no, Bucerotidae
## no, Buphagidae
## no, Burhinidae
## no, Cacatuidae
## no, Calcariidae
## no, Callaeidae
## no, Calyptomenidae
## no, Cardinalidae
## no, Cariamidae
## no, Casuariidae
## no, Cathartidae
## no, Certhiidae
## no, Cettiidae
## no, Chionidae
## no, Chloropseidae
## no, Ciconiidae
## no, Cinclidae
## no, Cinclosomatidae
## no, Climacteridae
## no, Coliidae
## no, Conopophagidae
## no, Coraciidae
## no, Corcoracidae
## no, Cotingidae
## no, Dasyornithidae
## no, Dicaeidae

```

no, Dicruridae
no, Donacobiidae
no, Dromadidae
no, Estrildidae
no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae
no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae
no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreoicidae
no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae
no, Pelecanidae
no, Pellorneidae
no, Phaethontidae
no, Philepittidae
no, Phoenicopteridae
no, Phoeniculidae
no, Phylloscopidae
no, Picathartidae
no, Pipridae

```
## no, Pittidae
## no, Pluvianidae
## no, Podargidae
## no, Podicipedidae
## no, Polioptilidae
## no, Promeropidae
## no, Prunellidae
## no, Psittacidae
## no, Psophiidae
## no, Ptiliogonatidae
## no, Ptilonorhynchidae
## no, Ramphastidae
## no, Recurvirostridae
## no, Regulidae
## no, Remizidae
## no, Rheidae
## no, Rhinocryptidae
## no, Rhipiduridae
## no, Rhynochetidae
## no, Rostratulidae
## no, Sagittariidae
## no, Sarothruridae
## no, Scopidae
## no, Sittidae
## no, Steatornithidae
## no, Stercorariidae
## no, Strigopidae
## no, Struthionidae
## no, Thamnophilidae
## no, Thinocoridae
## no, Thraupidae
## no, Tichodromidae
## no, Timaliidae
## no, Tinamidae
## no, Todidae
## no, Trogonidae
## no, Turnicidae
## no, Tytonidae
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(FEM, fill = "coral", bins = 20)
```



```

comboC5 <- data.frame(ffam, FEM,FEMlow,FEMup, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for each fami
colnames(comboC5) <- c("Family", "FEMmass", "FEMlow", "FEMup", "Rsq", "Nspecies")

write.csv(comboC5, "famCOEFFSfemAS.csv") #Table S9b

####only PC2relegg as predictor
numx = 0
EGG = FEM = CS = HWI = 0
FEMlow = FEMup =EGGlow =EGGup =CSlow =CSup =HWIlow =HWIup = 0
MNrelegg = 0
r2 = 0
obs = 0
ct = ffam = 0

for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
  numx <- nrow(datx)
  if (numx >4 ) {
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat15 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
    modC6 <- lm(RC2EL ~ PC2relegg, data = dat15)
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
    #print(summary(modC6))
    CONF <- confint(modC6)
    EGG[ct] = modC6$coefficients[2]
    EGGlow[ct] = CONF[2,1]
  }
}

```

```

EGGup[ct] =CONF[2,2]
rsq <- r2(modC6)
r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1]
obs[ct] <- nobs(modC6)
} else {
  cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
}
}
}

```

```

## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
## no, Balaenicipitidae
## no, Bombycillidae
## no, Bucconidae
## no, Bucerotidae
## no, Buphagidae
## no, Burhinidae
## no, Cacatuidae
## no, Calcariidae
## no, Callaeidae
## no, Calyptomenidae
## no, Cardinalidae
## no, Cariamidae
## no, Casuariidae
## no, Cathartidae
## no, Certhiidae
## no, Cettiidae
## no, Chionidae
## no, Chloropseidae
## no, Ciconiidae
## no, Cinclidae
## no, Cinclosomatidae
## no, Climacteridae
## no, Coliidae
## no, Conopophagidae
## no, Coraciidae
## no, Corcoracidae
## no, Cotingidae
## no, Dasyornithidae
## no, Dicaeidae
## no, Dicruridae
## no, Donacobiidae
## no, Dromadidae
## no, Estrildidae

```

no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae
no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae
no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreoicidae
no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae
no, Pelecanidae
no, Pellorneidae
no, Phaethontidae
no, Philepittidae
no, Phoenicopteridae
no, Phoeniculidae
no, Phylloscopidae
no, Picathartidae
no, Pipridae
no, Pittidae
no, Pluvianidae
no, Podargidae
no, Podicipedidae

```
## no, Polioptilidae
## no, Promeropidae
## no, Prunellidae
## no, Psittacidae
## no, Psophiidae
## no, Ptiliogonatidae
## no, Ptilonorhynchidae
## no, Ramphastidae
## no, Recurvirostridae
## no, Regulidae
## no, Remizidae
## no, Rheidae
## no, Rhinocryptidae
## no, Rhipiduridae
## no, Rhynochetidae
## no, Rostratulidae
## no, Sagittariidae
## no, Sarothruridae
## no, Scopidae
## no, Sittidae
## no, Steatornithidae
## no, Stercorariidae
## no, Strigopidae
## no, Struthionidae
## no, Thamnophilidae
## no, Thinocoridae
## no, Thraupidae
## no, Tichodromidae
## no, Timaliidae
## no, Tinamidae
## no, Todidae
## no, Trogonidae
## no, Turnicidae
## no, Tytonidae
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(EGG, fill = "coral", bins = 20)
```



```

comboC6 <- data.frame(ffam, EGG,EGGlow,EGGup, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for each fami
colnames(comboC6) <- c("Family", "EGG","EGGlow","EGGup","Rsq","Nspecies")

write.csv(comboC6, "famCOEFFSreleggAS.csv") #Table S9b

###only clutch size as predictor
numx = 0
EGG = FEM = CS = HWI = 0
FEMlow = FEMup =EGGlow =EGGup =CSlow =CSup =HWIlow =HWIup = 0
MNrelegg = 0
r2 = 0
obs = 0
ct = ffam = 0

for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
  numx <- nrow(datx)
  if (numx >4 ) {
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat16 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
    modC7 <- lm(RC2EL ~ sCSegg, data = dat16)
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
    #print(summary(modC7))
    CONF <- confint(modC7)
    CS[ct] = modC7$coefficients[2]
    CSlow[ct] = CONF[2,1]
  }
}

```

```

CSup[ct] = CONF[2,2]
rsq <- r2(modC7)
r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1]
obs[ct] <- nobs(modC7)
} else {
  cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
}
}
}

```

```

## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
## no, Balaenicipitidae
## no, Bombycillidae
## no, Bucconidae
## no, Bucerotidae
## no, Buphagidae
## no, Burhinidae
## no, Cacatuidae
## no, Calcariidae
## no, Callaeidae
## no, Calyptomenidae
## no, Cardinalidae
## no, Cariamidae
## no, Casuariidae
## no, Cathartidae
## no, Certhiidae
## no, Cettiidae
## no, Chionidae
## no, Chloropseidae
## no, Ciconiidae
## no, Cinclidae
## no, Cinclosomatidae
## no, Climacteridae
## no, Coliidae
## no, Conopophagidae
## no, Coraciidae
## no, Corcoracidae
## no, Cotingidae
## no, Dasyornithidae
## no, Dicaeidae
## no, Dicruridae
## no, Donacobiidae
## no, Dromadidae
## no, Estrildidae

```

no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae
no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae
no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreoicidae
no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae
no, Pelecanidae
no, Pellorneidae
no, Phaethontidae
no, Philepittidae
no, Phoenicopteridae
no, Phoeniculidae
no, Phylloscopidae
no, Picathartidae
no, Pipridae
no, Pittidae
no, Pluvianidae
no, Podargidae
no, Podicipedidae

```
## no, Polioptilidae
## no, Promeropidae
## no, Prunellidae
## no, Psittacidae
## no, Psophiidae
## no, Ptiliogonatidae
## no, Ptilonorhynchidae
## no, Ramphastidae
## no, Recurvirostridae
## no, Regulidae
## no, Remizidae
## no, Rheidae
## no, Rhinocryptidae
## no, Rhipiduridae
## no, Rhynochetidae
## no, Rostratulidae
## no, Sagittariidae
## no, Sarothruridae
## no, Scopidae
## no, Sittidae
## no, Steatornithidae
## no, Stercorariidae
## no, Strigopidae
## no, Struthionidae
## no, Thamnophilidae
## no, Thinocoridae
## no, Thraupidae
## no, Tichodromidae
## no, Timaliidae
## no, Tinamidae
## no, Todidae
## no, Trogonidae
## no, Turnicidae
## no, Tytonidae
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(CS, fill = "coral", bins = 20)
```

```
## Warning: Removed 4 rows containing non-finite values (stat_bin).
```



```

comboC7 <- data.frame(ffam, CS,CSlow,CSup, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for each family
colnames(comboC7) <- c("Family","CS","CSlow","CSup", "Rsq","Nspecies")

write.csv(comboC7, "famCOEFFScsAS.csv") #Table S9b

#####only HWI as predictor
numx = 0
EGG = FEM = CS = HWI = 0
FEMlow = FEMup =EGGlow =EGGup =CSlow =CSup =HWIlow =HWIup = 0
MNrelegg = 0
r2 = 0
obs = 0
ct = ffam = 0

for(i in 1:Nfams){ #analyses for each family with 5 or more species, no interaction terms
  datx <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
  numx <- nrow(datx)
  if (numx >4 ) {
    ct = ct+1
    ffam[ct] = fams[i]
    dat17 <- subset(dat1neoNA, Family == fams[i])
    modC8 <- lm(RC2EL ~ sHWI, data = dat17)
    #print(fams[i]) #puts the family name before each summary output
    #print(summary(modC8))
    CONF <- confint(modC8)
    HWI[ct] = modC8$coefficients[2]
    HWIlow[ct] = CONF[2,1]
  }
}

```

```

HWIup[ct] = CONF[2,2]
rsq <- r2( modC8)
r2[ct] <- rsq$R2[1]
obs[ct] <- nobs( modC8)
} else {
  cat ("no, ", (fams[i]), "\n")
}
}
}

```

```

## no, Acanthisittidae
## no, Acanthizidae
## no, Aegithalidae
## no, Aegithinidae
## no, Aegothelidae
## no, Anhimidae
## no, Anhingidae
## no, Anseranatidae
## no, Apodidae
## no, Apterygidae
## no, Aramidae
## no, Artamidae
## no, Balaenicipitidae
## no, Bombycillidae
## no, Bucconidae
## no, Bucerotidae
## no, Buphagidae
## no, Burhinidae
## no, Cacatuidae
## no, Calcariidae
## no, Callaeidae
## no, Calyptomenidae
## no, Cardinalidae
## no, Cariamidae
## no, Casuariidae
## no, Cathartidae
## no, Certhiidae
## no, Cettiidae
## no, Chionidae
## no, Chloropseidae
## no, Ciconiidae
## no, Cinclidae
## no, Cinclosomatidae
## no, Climacteridae
## no, Coliidae
## no, Conopophagidae
## no, Coraciidae
## no, Corcoracidae
## no, Cotingidae
## no, Dasyornithidae
## no, Dicaeidae
## no, Dicruridae
## no, Donacobiidae
## no, Dromadidae
## no, Estrildidae

```

no, Eurypygidae
no, Fregatidae
no, Furnariidae
no, Galbulidae
no, Gaviidae
no, Glareolidae
no, Grallariidae
no, Haematopodidae
no, Heliornithidae
no, Hemiprocnidae
no, Hirundinidae
no, Hydrobatidae
no, Hypocoliidae
no, Ibidorhynchidae
no, Indicatoridae
no, Irenidae
no, Laniidae
no, Locustellidae
no, Lybiidae
no, Malaconotidae
no, Maluridae
no, Megalaimidae
no, Menuridae
no, Mesitornithidae
no, Momotidae
no, Monarchidae
no, Musophagidae
no, Neosittidae
no, Numididae
no, Nyctibiidae
no, Oceanitidae
no, Odontophoridae
no, Opisthocomidae
no, Oreoicidae
no, Oriolidae
no, Pachycephalidae
no, Pandionidae
no, Panuridae
no, Parulidae
no, Passerellidae
no, Pedionomidae
no, Pelecanidae
no, Pellorneidae
no, Phaethontidae
no, Philepittidae
no, Phoenicopteridae
no, Phoeniculidae
no, Phylloscopidae
no, Picathartidae
no, Pipridae
no, Pittidae
no, Pluvianidae
no, Podargidae
no, Podicipedidae

```
## no, Polioptilidae
## no, Promeropidae
## no, Prunellidae
## no, Psittacidae
## no, Psophiidae
## no, Ptiliogonatidae
## no, Ptilonorhynchidae
## no, Ramphastidae
## no, Recurvirostridae
## no, Regulidae
## no, Remizidae
## no, Rheidae
## no, Rhinocryptidae
## no, Rhipiduridae
## no, Rhynochetidae
## no, Rostratulidae
## no, Sagittariidae
## no, Sarothruridae
## no, Scopidae
## no, Sittidae
## no, Steatornithidae
## no, Stercorariidae
## no, Strigopidae
## no, Struthionidae
## no, Thamnophilidae
## no, Thinocoridae
## no, Thraupidae
## no, Tichodromidae
## no, Timaliidae
## no, Tinamidae
## no, Todidae
## no, Trogonidae
## no, Turnicidae
## no, Tytonidae
## no, Upupidae
## no, Vangidae
## no, Vireonidae
## no, Zosteropidae
```

```
qplot(HWI, fill = "coral", bins = 20)
```



```

comboC8 <- data.frame(ffam, HWI,HWIlow, HWIup, r2, obs) #make a dataframe of the estimates for each fam
colnames(comboC8) <- c("Family", "HWI", "HWIlow", "HWIup", "Rsq", "Nspecies")

write.csv(comboC8, "famCOEFFShwiAS.csv") #Table S9b

```

6 LOAD PHYLOGENY

All data and phylogenies; Figure S1

```

ALLphy <- read.nexus("Ericson1000.nex") #tree set downloaded from birdtree
rownames(dat1) <- dat1[,5]
dat1[,5] <- NULL
ALLphydat <- dat1

ALLphydat$SPC1mass = as.numeric(scale(ALLphydat$PC1mass))
ALLphydat$SPC2relegg = as.numeric(scale(ALLphydat$PC2relegg))
ALLphydat$sCSeg = as.numeric(scale(ALLphydat$CSeg))
ALLphydat$SHWI = as.numeric(scale(ALLphydat$HWI))

ALLphydat <- ALLphydat %>% mutate(sPC1mass = scale(PC1mass), sPC2relegg = scale(PC2relegg))

name.check(ALLphy[[1]], ALLphydat) #check to see that scientific names in phylogeny match those in data

## $tree_not_data
## character(0)
##
## $data_not_tree

```

```
## [1] "Brachypteryx_cruralis"      "Chlamydotis_macqueenii"
## [3] "Corvus_cornix"                "Ectopistes_migratorius"
## [5] "Gallinula_pacifica"          "Gallirallus_modestus"
## [7] "Pinguinus_impennis"          "Rhodonessa_caryophyllacea"
## [9] "Turnagra_capensis"
```

7 MAIN DATA and PHYLOGENY SUBSETS

7.1 Main subsets for neognaths and paleognaths

```
#paleognaths
paleo <- c("Struthioniformes", "Casuariiformes", "Rheiformes", "Apterygiformes", "Tinamiformes")
PALEOphydat <- ALLphydat %>% filter(Order %in% paleo)
tmp <- name.check(ALLphy[[1]], PALEOphydat)
PALEOphy <- drop.tip(ALLphy[[1]], tip=tmp$tree_not_data) #drops tips that do not match

ALLphy1 <- ALLphy[[1]] #first tree in the set of 1000
#neognaths
NEOphydat <- ALLphydat %>% filter(!Order %in% paleo) #remove species of paleognaths
tmp <- name.check(ALLphy1, NEOphydat)
NEOphy <- drop.tip(ALLphy1, tip=tmp$tree_not_data) #drops tips that do not match
```

8 PELVIS ANATOMY

8.1 Load data and phylogeny for the pelvis anatomy dataset

```
PELVISphy <- read.nexus("PELVIStree.nex") #tree set downloaded from birdtree
PELVISphy1 <- PELVISphy[[1]]
name.check(PELVISphy1, dat2) #check to see that scientific names in phylogeny match those in dataset
```

```
## [1] "OK"
```

8.2 HWI vs pelvis anatomy

8.2.1 Correlations and models to predict HWI, all species

Excluding flightless species; Tables S14, S15; Figure S7

```
dat2NF <- dat2 %>% filter(!LOCO == "F") %>% droplevels() #exclude flightless species

#Correlations among variables
correlation(dat2NF[, c("HWI", "avLS", "avWacet", "avWish", "avLRpostpre", "avLRilanti", "RC1meas", "RC2ra
```

```
## # Correlation Matrix (pearson-method)
##
## Parameter1 | Parameter2 | r | 95% CI | t(169) | p
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
## HWI | avLS | 0.31 | [ 0.17, 0.44] | 4.23 | < .001***
## HWI | avWacet | 0.29 | [ 0.14, 0.42] | 3.90 | 0.002**
## HWI | avWish | 0.37 | [ 0.23, 0.49] | 5.10 | < .001***
## HWI | avLRpostpre | -0.04 | [-0.19, 0.11] | -0.51 | > .999
## HWI | avLRilanti | 0.27 | [ 0.12, 0.40] | 3.62 | 0.004**
## HWI | RC1meas | 0.46 | [ 0.33, 0.57] | 6.75 | < .001***
## HWI | RC2ratios | 0.02 | [-0.14, 0.16] | 0.20 | > .999
```

```

## avLS      |      avWacet | 0.76 | [ 0.69, 0.82] | 15.38 | < .001***
## avLS      |      avWish  | 0.85 | [ 0.80, 0.89] | 20.88 | < .001***
## avLS      | avLRpostpre | 0.24 | [ 0.09, 0.37] | 3.15  | 0.019*
## avLS      | avLRilanti  | 0.66 | [ 0.56, 0.73] | 11.28 | < .001***
## avLS      |      RC1meas | 0.87 | [ 0.83, 0.90] | 22.86 | < .001***
## avLS      |      RC2ratios | 0.31 | [ 0.17, 0.44] | 4.31  | < .001***
## avWacet   |      avWish  | 0.86 | [ 0.81, 0.89] | 21.51 | < .001***
## avWacet   | avLRpostpre | -0.17 | [-0.31, -0.02] | -2.23 | 0.218
## avWacet   | avLRilanti  | 0.12 | [-0.03, 0.27] | 1.59  | 0.565
## avWacet   |      RC1meas | 0.90 | [ 0.86, 0.92] | 26.28 | < .001***
## avWacet   |      RC2ratios | -0.21 | [-0.35, -0.06] | -2.74 | 0.061
## avWish    | avLRpostpre | 0.16 | [ 0.01, 0.31] | 2.15  | 0.229
## avWish    | avLRilanti  | 0.33 | [ 0.19, 0.45] | 4.49  | < .001***
## avWish    |      RC1meas | 0.88 | [ 0.84, 0.91] | 23.76 | < .001***
## avWish    |      RC2ratios | 0.13 | [-0.02, 0.28] | 1.74  | 0.504
## avLRpostpre | avLRilanti  | 0.51 | [ 0.39, 0.62] | 7.76  | < .001***
## avLRpostpre |      RC1meas | -0.08 | [-0.23, 0.07] | -1.04 | > .999
## avLRpostpre |      RC2ratios | 0.92 | [ 0.90, 0.94] | 31.53 | < .001***
## avLRilanti |      RC1meas | 0.40 | [ 0.26, 0.52] | 5.64  | < .001***
## avLRilanti |      RC2ratios | 0.71 | [ 0.63, 0.78] | 13.19 | < .001***
## RC1meas   |      RC2ratios | -0.03 | [-0.18, 0.12] | -0.41 | > .999
##
## p-value adjustment method: Holm (1979)
## Observations: 171

```

```
(nfamilies <- dat2NF %>% group_by(Family) %>% summarise(number = n(), na.rm=TRUE))
```

```

## # A tibble: 47 x 3
##   Family      number na.rm
##   <fct>      <int> <lg1>
## 1 Accipitridae      21 TRUE
## 2 Aegithalidae       1 TRUE
## 3 Alaudidae         4 TRUE
## 4 Alcedinidae       1 TRUE
## 5 Alcidae           1 TRUE
## 6 Anatidae          16 TRUE
## 7 Apodidae          1 TRUE
## 8 Ardeidae           8 TRUE
## 9 Burhinidae        1 TRUE
## 10 Caprimulgidae    1 TRUE
## # ... with 37 more rows

```

```
(nbirds <- dat2NF %>% summarise(number = n()))
```

```

##   number
## 1     171

```

```
#Models to predict HWI, controlling for phylogeny
```

```
modD1<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(logADmass) +scale(RC1meas)*LOCO, phy = PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model ="
```

```

## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(logADmass) + scale(RC1meas) * LOCO, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 2 taxa with missing data

```

```
summary(modD1) #Table S15
```

```

##
## Call:

```

```

## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(logADmass) + scale(RC1meas) * LOCOC,
## data = dat2NF, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 1111.5 -544.7
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -17.4795  -4.7879   0.0082   5.7939  18.7249
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9441517
## sigma2: 0.9010023
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI
## (Intercept)    49.733080    5.830252    8.530177   38.508683   62.9194
## scale(logADmass) -0.452653    0.946517   -0.478230  -2.089673    1.3001
## scale(RC1meas)  -5.065190    1.830741   -2.766743  -9.187426   -1.3629
## LOCOC          -10.805718    3.947354   -2.737458 -18.347792   -3.8506
## LOCOP          -15.670858    4.192998   -3.737387 -23.033712   -7.3308
## LOCOS          -2.569704    3.959851   -0.648940  -9.197884    4.1196
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOC  4.937173    2.425423    2.035593  -0.077918   10.0804
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOP  9.477092    2.319228    4.086313    5.693314   13.8601
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOS  1.205019    3.019923    0.399023  -4.722282    7.5700
##              p.value
## (Intercept)    9.880e-15 ***
## scale(logADmass)  0.6331313
## scale(RC1meas)   0.0063206 **
## LOCOC           0.0068838 **
## LOCOP           0.0002574 ***
## LOCOS           0.5172964
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOC 0.0434206 *
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOP 6.879e-05 ***
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOS 0.6904017
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.2143    Adjusted R-squared: 0.1756
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9441517.
##
## sigma2: 0.9010023
## bootstrap mean: 0.8360022 (on raw scale)
##                0.8217556 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.5750753,1.163982)
##
## lambda: 0.9441517
## bootstrap mean: 0.9356684 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.8741358,0.9798578)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modD1)
```

```
## [1] 171
```

```
modPD1<- phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass +RC1meas*LOCO, phy = PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass + RC1meas * LOCO, phy = PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, : will drop from the tree 2 taxa with missing data
```

```
visreg(modPD1, xvar = "RC1meas", by = "LOCO", overlay=TRUE, band = TRUE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE)
```



```
modD2<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(logADmass) +scale(RC2ratios)*LOCO, phy = PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(logADmass) + scale(RC2ratios) * LOCO, phy = PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 2 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modD2) #Table S15
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(logADmass) + scale(RC2ratios) *  
## LOCO, data = dat2NF, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)
```

```
##
```

```
## AIC logLik
```

```
## 1126.2 -552.1
```

```
##
```

```
## Raw residuals:
```

```
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max  
## -17.3323 -6.6799 -0.8972  5.4844 18.9333
```

```
##
```

```
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
```

```

## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9583357
## sigma2: 1.053289
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI
## (Intercept)      51.94402    6.54426   7.93734   40.76781   64.2664
## scale(logADmass)  -1.07477    0.80937  -1.32791  -2.06256    0.4173
## scale(RC2ratios)  3.07652    2.41613   1.27333  -1.00811    9.8798
## LOCOC            -13.12604    4.42982  -2.96311  -22.94326  -7.6271
## LOCOP            -21.88096    4.81266  -4.54654  -30.05938 -13.7791
## LOCOS            -2.85356    4.85625  -0.58761  -14.84510   4.5319
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOC -3.76591    3.84974  -0.97822  -11.94378   2.2099
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOP -4.97363    3.34443  -1.48714  -11.50572   1.0222
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOS -4.54156    2.92738  -1.55141  -10.35945  -0.1211
##           p.value
## (Intercept)      3.237e-13 ***
## scale(logADmass)  0.186077
## scale(RC2ratios)  0.204726
## LOCOC            0.003505 **
## LOCOP            1.063e-05 ***
## LOCOS            0.557615
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOC 0.329422
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOP 0.138922
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOS 0.122755
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.137 Adjusted R-squared: 0.09436
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9583357.
##
## sigma2: 1.053289
##   bootstrap mean: 0.9484978 (on raw scale)
##   0.9336201 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6373718,1.266168)
##
## lambda: 0.9583357
##   bootstrap mean: 0.9497529 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.8656709,0.9852157)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
modPLD2<- phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass +RC2ratios*LOC0, phy = PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model ="lambda", bo
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass + RC2ratios * LOC0, phy = PELVISphy1, : will
## drop from the tree 2 taxa with missing data
visreg(modPLD2, xvar ="RC2ratios",by = "LOC0", overlay=TRUE, band = TRUE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=

```


8.2.2 Models to predict HWI, for each mode of locomotion

Table S16, Figure S8

```
#aerial
modE1 <- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "A")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 134 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modE1)
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), data = subset(dat2NF,
##   LOCO == "A"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 240.2 -115.1
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -16.080 -6.377 -1.713  6.882 15.192
##
## Mean tip height: 88.39294
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9545818
## sigma2: 0.7337613
##
## Coefficients:
##               Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
```

```

## (Intercept)      49.05715   3.17821 15.43548   43.07008   55.2656 < 2e-16 ***
## scale(RC1meas)  -3.98646   1.55552 -2.56277   -6.81272   -1.4095 0.01471 *
## scale(logADmass) 0.24987   1.49113  0.16757   -2.26771    2.5941 0.86786
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.2974    Adjusted R-squared: 0.2584
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9545818.
##
## sigma2: 0.7337613
##   bootstrap mean: 0.7172988 (on raw scale)
##                   0.6722456 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.2498097,1.280679)
##
## lambda: 0.9545818
##   bootstrap mean: 0.9325895 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7010954,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modE1)
```

```
## [1] 39
```

```
modE2 <- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "A"))
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 134 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modE2)
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),
## data = subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "A"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda",
## boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 245.1 -117.6
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -17.166 -7.705 -1.482  3.804 18.603
##
## Mean tip height: 88.39294
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9675884
## sigma2: 0.8939014
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept)  49.70157  3.50041 14.19880   42.34643   56.1287 2.526e-16
## scale(RC2ratios)  1.41009  1.18394  1.19101   -0.46809    4.3263 0.24144
## scale(logADmass) -2.43464  0.98458 -2.47276   -3.87855   -0.1381 0.01826
##

```

```
## (Intercept)      ***
## scale(RC2ratios)
## scale(logADmass) *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.2042    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1599
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9675884.
##
## sigma2: 0.8939014
##      bootstrap mean: 0.843968 (on raw scale)
##                   0.7985011 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.3777644,1.358049)
##
## lambda: 0.9675884
##      bootstrap mean: 0.952322 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.8032141,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modE2)
```

```
## [1] 39
```

```
#cursorial
```

```
modE3<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) +scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "C"), r
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 135 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modE3)
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), data = subset(dat2NF,
##   LOCO == "C"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 261.2 -125.6
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -15.933  -6.548  -1.496   6.963  20.096
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1
## sigma2: 0.9493927
##
## Coefficients:
##      Estimate  StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept)  37.08307  6.14439  6.03528   27.22936   47.9796 6.938e-07
## scale(RC1meas) -0.35201  1.48429 -0.23716   -2.99896    2.0116  0.8139
## scale(logADmass) -0.43449  1.25452 -0.34634   -2.93115    1.9103  0.7312
##
```

```

## (Intercept)      ***
## scale(RC1meas)
## scale(logADmass)
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.009583  Adjusted R-squared:  -0.04701
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1.
##
## sigma2: 0.9493927
##      bootstrap mean: 0.7559984 (on raw scale)
##                   0.7144632 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.3240251,1.24049)
##
## lambda: 1
##      bootstrap mean: 0.9493205 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7604678,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modE3)
```

```
## [1] 38
```

```
modE4<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) +scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "C"),
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 135 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modE4)
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),
## data = subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "C"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda",
## boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 261.3 -125.6
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -16.069  -6.353  -1.040   6.456  19.856
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1
## sigma2: 0.9498443
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept)  37.03313   6.13894  6.03250   25.64334   45.8072 6.997e-07
## scale(RC2ratios) -0.25488  1.28121 -0.19894   -2.96799    2.5958  0.8435
## scale(logADmass) -0.60907  1.10222 -0.55259   -2.93438    1.4452  0.5841
##

```

```

## (Intercept)      ***
## scale(RC2ratios)
## scale(logADmass)
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.009112  Adjusted R-squared:  -0.04751
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1.
##
## sigma2: 0.9498443
##      bootstrap mean: 0.7705554 (on raw scale)
##                   0.7238693 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.2771397,1.269559)
##
## lambda: 1
##      bootstrap mean: 0.9209905 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.3532855,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
#perching
modE5<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) +scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "P"), m

## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 103 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, : the estimation of lambda
## You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
summary(modE5)

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), data = subset(dat2NF,
##   LOCO == "P"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 460.6 -225.3
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -15.5892 -2.4923 -0.7315  3.4179 16.9725
##
## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.4004192
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI
## (Intercept)  29.803812  0.739059  40.326702   28.695225   31.5925
## scale(RC1meas)  5.010236  0.994876  5.036041    3.155597    7.0173
## scale(logADmass) -0.038154  0.994876 -0.038350   -2.123065    2.0534
##
##              p.value
## (Intercept)  < 2.2e-16 ***

```

```

## scale(RC1meas) 3.821e-06 ***
## scale(logADmass) 0.9695
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.401 Adjusted R-squared: 0.3831
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.4004192
## bootstrap mean: 0.3876591 (on raw scale)
## 0.3818679 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.2729664,0.5269359)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
## bootstrap mean: 0.01931866 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.3079416)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
nobs(modE5)

## [1] 70
modE6<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) +scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "P"),
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 103 taxa with missing data
summary(modE6)

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),
## data = subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "P"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda",
## boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 469.8 -229.9
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -18.045 -7.390 -2.188 1.745 14.644
##
## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.6005462
## sigma2: 0.6741481
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) 31.96407 2.69605 11.85591 26.67084 39.1127 <2e-16 ***
## scale(RC2ratios) -1.94340 1.26589 -1.53520 -4.01079 0.2237 0.1294
## scale(logADmass) 0.66435 0.97628 0.68049 -1.37715 2.7568 0.4985
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

##
## R-squared: 0.05137   Adjusted R-squared: 0.02306
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.6005462.
##
## sigma2: 0.6741481
##   bootstrap mean: 0.6191868 (on raw scale)
##                 0.5921884 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.3455053,1.005711)
##
## lambda: 0.6005462
##   bootstrap mean: 0.4962747 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.8535651)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
#swimming
modE7<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) +scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "S"),
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 149 taxa with missing data
summary(modE7)

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), data = subset(dat2NF,
##   LOCO == "S"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 158.33 -74.16
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -17.277  -1.796   2.380   5.444  11.358
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9386108
## sigma2: 0.8352593
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept)  47.968012  6.145527  7.805354   37.177162   59.7400  1.22e-07
## scale(RC1meas) -0.254624  3.328239 -0.076504  -5.485004    4.5341  0.9397
## scale(logADmass) -2.156241  3.083545 -0.699273  -6.107585    2.4928  0.4921
##
## (Intercept)      ***
## scale(RC1meas)
## scale(logADmass)
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.1465   Adjusted R-squared: 0.0652
##

```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9386108.
##
## sigma2: 0.8352593
##   bootstrap mean: 0.6388681 (on raw scale)
##                   0.5038758 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.1141761,1.568674)
##
## lambda: 0.9386108
##   bootstrap mean: 0.7595259 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modE7)
```

```
## [1] 24
```

```
modE8<- phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) +scale(logADmass), phy = PELVISphy1, subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "S"),
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 149 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modE8)
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = HWI ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),
##   data = subset(dat2NF, LOCO == "S"), phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda",
##   boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 157.93 -73.97
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -16.447 -2.150  1.728  5.479 11.476
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9331603
## sigma2: 0.7968408
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept)  48.35854  5.96022  8.11355   38.90694   60.9489 6.565e-08
## scale(RC2ratios) -1.02681  1.72743 -0.59441   -4.43581    1.5480  0.5586
## scale(logADmass) -1.95798  1.45843 -1.34253   -4.38434    0.8729  0.1938
##
## (Intercept)    ***
## scale(RC2ratios)
## scale(logADmass)
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.1656   Adjusted R-squared: 0.08611
##
```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9331603.
##
## sigma2: 0.7968408
##   bootstrap mean: 0.5919047 (on raw scale)
##                   0.4947902 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.13002,1.217146)
##
## lambda: 0.9331603
##   bootstrap mean: 0.7925126 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
#Strigiformes
dat2strig <- dat2NF/>% filter(Order == "STRIGIFORMES")
modE9 <- phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass + RC2ratios, phy = PELVISphy1, data = dat2strig) #model = "lambda", boot=
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass + RC2ratios, phy = PELVISphy1, data =
## dat2strig): will drop from the tree 167 taxa with missing data
```

```
visreg(modE9, xvar = "RC2ratios", points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE) #Figure S8
```



```
modE10 <- phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass + RC1meas, phy = PELVISphy1, data = dat2strig) #model = "lambda", boot=
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(HWI ~ logADmass + RC1meas, phy = PELVISphy1, data =
## dat2strig): will drop from the tree 167 taxa with missing data
```

```
visreg(modE10, xvar = "RC1meas", points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE) #Figure S8
```


8.3 Eggshape vs pelvis anatomy

8.3.1 General PGLS models for effect of pelvis size and shape on egg shape

Controlling for locomotion and excluding flightless species using dat2NF Figure 5c,d

```
#RC1meas, pelvis size; control for female size to get relative pelvis size
modF1 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas)*LOCO +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) * LOCO + PC1mass + PC2relegg, : will
## drop from the tree 32 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modF1) #Table S12; interactions NS at P>0.20
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) * LOCO + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NF, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 281.5 -128.8
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -2.0352 -0.4551 0.3181 0.7989 3.4464
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8782159
## sigma2: 0.007041988
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI
## (Intercept) -0.6777331 0.5211229 -1.3005244 -1.6277072 0.2758
```

```

## scale(RC1meas)      0.1096899  0.3424999  0.3202625  -0.3476627    0.8649
## LOCOC               0.8552938  0.3804217  2.2482779   0.1025317    1.3960
## LOCOP              0.3127923  0.4180715  0.7481788  -0.3831148    0.9887
## LOCOS              1.0964684  0.4107992  2.6691101   0.4419785    1.8465
## PC1mass            -0.1016931  0.3411004 -0.2981325  -0.7558111    0.5286
## PC2relegg         -0.0060485  0.0781386 -0.0774077  -0.1297843    0.1479
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOC -0.0962217  0.2758988 -0.3487573  -0.5545555    0.5021
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOP -0.0715871  0.2728961 -0.2623235  -0.6621475    0.3746
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOS -0.0432725  0.3448982 -0.1254645  -0.7171215    0.5566
##                p.value
## (Intercept)       0.195705
## scale(RC1meas)    0.749280
## LOCOC             0.026229 *
## LOCOP             0.455693
## LOCOS             0.008567 **
## PC1mass           0.766074
## PC2relegg         0.938417
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOC 0.727831
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOP 0.793484
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOS 0.900348
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.06109   Adjusted R-squared: -0.003415
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8782159.
##
## sigma2: 0.007041988
##   bootstrap mean: 0.006164182 (on raw scale)
##                 0.006025621 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003925038,0.00866091)
##
## lambda: 0.8782159
##   bootstrap mean: 0.8429469 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6884787,0.9525335)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modF1)
```

```
## [1] 141
```

```
modF2 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas)*LOCO +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model =
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) * LOCO + PC1mass + PC2relegg, : will
## drop from the tree 32 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modF2) #Table S12, interacton with swimming P=0.08
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) * LOCO + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
##         data = dat2NF, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##           AIC logLik
##      278.3 -127.1

```

```

##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.9892 -0.4038  0.3659  0.9625  2.3375
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8167933
## sigma2: 0.005922137
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI
## (Intercept)    -0.676162  0.468792  -1.442349   -1.330871    0.4085
## scale(RC1meas)  0.110000  0.340379  0.323171   -0.486335    0.6889
## LOCOC          0.308106  0.354262  0.869713   -0.297359    0.9397
## LOCOP         -0.162921  0.385370 -0.422764   -0.847694    0.4189
## LOCOS          1.224634  0.392866  3.117176    0.609785    1.9389
## PC1mass        0.170398  0.339299  0.502207   -0.345708    0.8665
## PC2relegg     -0.085754  0.077262 -1.109907   -0.218784    0.0390
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOC 0.131761  0.266922  0.493633   -0.352793    0.6338
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOP -0.031008  0.262819 -0.117982   -0.454786    0.4526
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOS 0.620310  0.342569  1.810760    0.073437    1.2360
##              p.value
## (Intercept)    0.151591
## scale(RC1meas) 0.747081
## LOCOC          0.386048
## LOCOP          0.673160
## LOCOS          0.002245 **
## PC1mass        0.616365
## PC2relegg     0.269072
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOC 0.622392
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOP 0.906263
## scale(RC1meas):LOCOS 0.072470 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.2726    Adjusted R-squared: 0.2226
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8167933.
##
## sigma2: 0.005922137
##   bootstrap mean: 0.005046096 (on raw scale)
##                 0.004908932 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.002990341,0.007720128)
##
## lambda: 0.8167933
##   bootstrap mean: 0.7335237 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.3956005,0.9026577)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modF2)
```

```
## [1] 141
```

```
#RC2ratios pelvis shape
```

```
modF3 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios)*LOC0 +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) * LOC0 + PC1mass + PC2relegg, : will  
## drop from the tree 32 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modF3) #Table S12, all pos, interactions NS
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) * LOC0 + PC1mass +  
## PC2relegg, data = dat2NF, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)  
##  
## AIC logLik  
## 278.1 -127.0  
##  
## Raw residuals:  
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -1.9173 -0.3493 0.2618 0.7304 3.1220  
##  
## Mean tip height: 132.0409  
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:  
## lambda : 0.8613105  
## sigma2: 0.00656993  
##  
## Coefficients:  
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  
## (Intercept) -0.7212128 0.5427881 -1.3287188 -1.5073483 0.3887  
## scale(RC2ratios) -0.0510365 0.2658149 -0.1920003 -0.5904396 0.3846  
## LOC0C 0.8283093 0.4102988 2.0187955 0.0635253 1.5192  
## LOC0P 0.4852955 0.4776851 1.0159319 -0.6171743 1.3764  
## LOC0S 1.2644930 0.4994670 2.5316848 0.2596708 2.0799  
## PC1mass -0.0015739 0.1262786 -0.0124637 -0.2311991 0.2466  
## PC2relegg 0.0032686 0.0778472 0.0419873 -0.1675148 0.1366  
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0C -0.3716728 0.4107776 -0.9048028 -1.1285281 0.3891  
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0P 0.3222911 0.3649513 0.8831073 -0.3666977 1.0034  
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0S -0.0897125 0.3361143 -0.2669107 -0.6563274 0.6143  
## p.value  
## (Intercept) 0.18625  
## scale(RC2ratios) 0.84804  
## LOC0C 0.04555 *  
## LOC0P 0.31153  
## LOC0S 0.01253 *  
## PC1mass 0.99007  
## PC2relegg 0.96657  
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0C 0.36723  
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0P 0.37880  
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0S 0.78996  
## ---  
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1  
##  
## R-squared: 0.0847 Adjusted R-squared: 0.02182  
##
```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8613105.
##
## sigma2: 0.00656993
##   bootstrap mean: 0.005657174 (on raw scale)
##                   0.005494229 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003612697,0.00801187)
##
## lambda: 0.8613105
##   bootstrap mean: 0.8092144 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6373259,0.934701)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modF3)
```

```
## [1] 141
```

```
modF4 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios)*LOC0 +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) * LOC0 + PC1mass + PC2relegg, : will
## drop from the tree 32 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modF4) #Table S12, all interaction P<0.20
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) * LOC0 + PC1mass +
##   PC2relegg, data = dat2NF, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda",
##   boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 272.4 -124.2
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.4851 -0.3303  0.1762  0.6848  2.6306
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8106008
## sigma2: 0.005605105
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI
## (Intercept)   -0.980007   0.498935  -1.964196   -1.922842   -0.1112
## scale(RC2ratios) -0.321947   0.257845  -1.248606   -0.801817    0.2077
## LOC0C         0.704722   0.386301   1.824283   -0.045369    1.4698
## LOC0P         0.539849   0.450696   1.197812   -0.218097    1.4670
## LOC0S         0.887560   0.486083   1.825943   -0.094056    1.6265
## PC1mass       0.398828   0.121337   3.286954    0.148316    0.6571
## PC2relegg    -0.042145   0.076193  -0.553131   -0.182328    0.1345
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0C  0.706506   0.397839   1.775859   -0.124819    1.4995
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0P  0.745868   0.353520   2.109832    0.011290    1.3319
## scale(RC2ratios):LOC0S  0.721939   0.325634   2.217028    0.079366    1.4132
##
##              p.value
## (Intercept)  0.05162 .
```

```

## scale(RC2ratios)      0.21404
## LOCOC                 0.07039 .
## LOCOP                 0.23315
## LOCOS                 0.07014 .
## PC1mass               0.00130 **
## PC2relegg            0.58112
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOC 0.07808 .
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOP 0.03677 *
## scale(RC2ratios):LOCOS 0.02835 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.3028    Adjusted R-squared:  0.2549
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8106008.
##
## sigma2: 0.005605105
##   bootstrap mean: 0.00486528 (on raw scale)
##                   0.004696697 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.002504742,0.007337044)
##
## lambda: 0.8106008
##   bootstrap mean: 0.7430708 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.3943322,0.9111915)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modF4)
```

```
## [1] 141
```

```
####PLOTS without standardizing the predictors
```

```
modPLF1 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ RC1meas * LOCO + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model="lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ RC1meas * LOCO + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 32 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modPLF1)
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ RC1meas * LOCO + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NF, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 281.5 -128.8
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -2.0352 -0.4551  0.3181  0.7989  3.4464
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8782159
## sigma2: 0.007041988
##

```

```

## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept) -0.6758268  0.5214053 -1.2961640 -1.7002610   0.3054 0.197198
## RC1meas      0.1105425  0.3451621  0.3202625 -0.4223027   0.6557 0.749280
## LOCOC        0.8536216  0.3791439  2.2514448  0.0913866   1.6073 0.026023
## LOCOP        0.3115482  0.4187382  0.7440166 -0.2787370   1.1216 0.458199
## LOCOS        1.0957164  0.4094420  2.6761213  0.2660097   1.9273 0.008399
## PC1mass      -0.1016931  0.3411004 -0.2981325 -0.7048901   0.6507 0.766074
## PC2relegg    -0.0060485  0.0781386 -0.0774077 -0.1418261   0.1294 0.938417
## RC1meas:LOCOC -0.0969697  0.2780434 -0.3487573 -0.5684296   0.3626 0.727831
## RC1meas:LOCOP -0.0721435  0.2750173 -0.2623235 -0.5933335   0.4260 0.793484
## RC1meas:LOCOS -0.0436088  0.3475791 -0.1254645 -0.6319109   0.5210 0.900348
##
## (Intercept)
## RC1meas
## LOCOC      *
## LOCOP
## LOCOS      **
## PC1mass
## PC2relegg
## RC1meas:LOCOC
## RC1meas:LOCOP
## RC1meas:LOCOS
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.06109   Adjusted R-squared: -0.003415
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8782159.
##
## sigma2: 0.007041988
##      bootstrap mean: 0.006148358 (on raw scale)
##                   0.005998734 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003684433,0.008625071)
##
## lambda: 0.8782159
##      bootstrap mean: 0.8463538 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6462703,0.9493721)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
visreg(modPLF1, xvar = "RC1meas", by = "LOCOC", overlay=TRUE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE) #Figure 5c
```



```
modPLF2 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ RC2ratios*LOC0 +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NF, model="1")
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ RC2ratios * LOC0 + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 32 taxa with missing data
VPLF2 <- visreg(modPLF2, xvar = "RC2ratios", by = "LOC0", overlay=TRUE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE)
```


8.3.2 Models for each mode of locomotion

Tables S13; Figure 5a,b

```
dat2NFs <- dat2NF %>% filter(LOCO == "S")
dat2NFa <- dat2NF %>% filter(LOCO == "A")
dat2NFc <- dat2NF %>% filter(LOCO == "C")
dat2NFp <- dat2NF %>% filter(LOCO == "P")

### Aerial
modG1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFa, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 145 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG1) #Table S13
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NFa, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 71.94 -29.97
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.53583 -1.19865 -0.66021  0.08777  2.16581
##
## Mean tip height: 88.39294
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.7977177
## sigma2: 0.00936555
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)  -0.364966  0.377994 -0.965535  -0.955511    0.2809  0.3439
## scale(RC2ratios) -0.195295  0.189354 -1.031376  -0.608024    0.1052  0.3126
## PC1mass       0.201583  0.288519  0.698680  -0.363508    0.7365  0.4915
## PC2relegg     -0.081939  0.165132 -0.496205  -0.448490    0.1856  0.6243
##
## R-squared: 0.09817   Adjusted R-squared: -0.01456
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7977177.
##
## sigma2: 0.00936555
## bootstrap mean: 0.006597756 (on raw scale)
##                0.006026455 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.002331451,0.01230899)
##
## lambda: 0.7977177
## bootstrap mean: 0.5702633 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modG1)
```

```
## [1] 28
```

```
modPLG1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFa, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :  
## will drop from the tree 145 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modPLG1) #Table S13
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = dat2NFa,
```

```
## phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
##
```

```
## AIC logLik
```

```
## 71.94 -29.97
```

```
##
```

```
## Raw residuals:
```

```
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
```

```
## -1.53583 -1.19865 -0.66021 0.08777 2.16581
```

```
##
```

```
## Mean tip height: 88.39294
```

```
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
```

```
## lambda : 0.7977177
```

```
## sigma2: 0.00936555
```

```
##
```

```
## Coefficients:
```

```
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
```

```
## (Intercept) -0.681007 0.492227 -1.383521 -1.543216 0.3017 0.1792
```

```
## RC2ratios -0.351494 0.340801 -1.031376 -1.029532 0.3362 0.3126
```

```
## PC1mass 0.201583 0.288519 0.698680 -0.343928 0.7233 0.4915
```

```
## PC2relegg -0.081939 0.165132 -0.496205 -0.407340 0.2348 0.6243
```

```
##
```

```
## R-squared: 0.09817 Adjusted R-squared: -0.01456
```

```
##
```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7977177.
```

```
##
```

```
## sigma2: 0.00936555
```

```
## bootstrap mean: 0.007905377 (on raw scale)
```

```
## 0.007107017 (on log scale, then back transformed)
```

```
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.002630712,0.01525213)
```

```
##
```

```
## lambda: 0.7977177
```

```
## bootstrap mean: 0.643378 (on raw scale)
```

```
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
```

```
##
```

```
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modPLG1)
```

```
## [1] 28
```

```
visreg(modPLG1, xvar = "RC2ratios", band = FALSE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE,, xlim=c(-2,4), ylim=c(-2,4))
```



```
modG2 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFa, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 145 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG2) #Table S13
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),
## data = dat2NFa, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 52.86 -21.43
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -1.0267 -0.4622 -0.1360 0.5677 1.8875
##
## Mean tip height: 88.39294
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.7723098
## sigma2: 0.004910686
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.229648 0.266549 -0.861561 -0.758932 0.2302 0.3971
## scale(RC2ratios) 0.015727 0.131438 0.119653 -0.214912 0.2965 0.9057
## scale(logADmass) 0.060320 0.122529 0.492295 -0.169898 0.2879 0.6268
##
## R-squared: 0.01055 Adjusted R-squared: -0.06861
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7723098.
```

```
##
## sigma2: 0.004910686
##   bootstrap mean: 0.004428135 (on raw scale)
##                   0.003905466 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001589172,0.01057837)
##
## lambda: 0.7723098
##   bootstrap mean: 0.5907685 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modG2)
```

```
## [1] 28
```

```
modG3 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas)+PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFa, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 145 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG3) #Table S13
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NFa, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 70.17 -29.09
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.7219 -0.8998 -0.4734  0.2488  1.5614
##
## Mean tip height: 88.39294
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.6907896
## sigma2: 0.007693017
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)   0.60017  0.69862  0.85908   -1.07251    1.7782  0.3988
## scale(RC1meas) 0.84347  0.53653  1.57209   -0.34827    1.6313  0.1290
## PC1mass       -1.14805  0.86092 -1.33352   -2.38263    0.8283  0.1949
## PC2relegg     -0.15251  0.15734 -0.96933   -0.45196    0.1692  0.3420
##
## R-squared: 0.1241   Adjusted R-squared: 0.01467
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.6907896.
##
## sigma2: 0.007693017
##   bootstrap mean: 0.006321179 (on raw scale)
##                   0.005687951 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.002377311,0.01346907)
##
```

```

## lambda: 0.6907896
##      bootstrap mean: 0.5077902 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
nobs(modG3)

## [1] 28
modPLG3 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFa, model = "lambda")

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 145 taxa with missing data
summary(modPLG3) #Table S13

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = dat2NFa,
##      phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 70.17 -29.09
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.7219 -0.8998 -0.4734  0.2488  1.5614
##
## Mean tip height: 88.39294
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.6907896
## sigma2: 0.007693017
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.050638  0.390128 -0.129797  -0.866556    0.7562  0.8978
## RC1meas      1.171380  0.745111  1.572088  -0.504859    2.6731  0.1290
## PC1mass     -1.148051  0.860915 -1.333524  -2.781108    0.9195  0.1949
## PC2relegg   -0.152511  0.157336 -0.969330  -0.452667    0.1406  0.3420
##
## R-squared: 0.1241      Adjusted R-squared: 0.01467
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.6907896.
##
## sigma2: 0.007693017
##      bootstrap mean: 0.005861548 (on raw scale)
##                  0.005228703 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.00212779,0.01269567)
##
## lambda: 0.6907896
##      bootstrap mean: 0.4379879 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.9992486)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modPLG3)
```

```
## [1] 28
```

```
visreg(modPLG3, xvar = "RC1meas", band = FALSE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE, xlim=c(-2,2), ylim=
```



```
modG4 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFa, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy =  
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 145 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG4) #Table S13
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass),  
## data = dat2NFa, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)  
##  
## AIC logLik  
## 52.84 -21.42  
##  
## Raw residuals:  
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -1.0198 -0.4746 -0.1402 0.5744 1.9234  
##  
## Mean tip height: 88.39294  
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:  
## lambda : 0.7767579  
## sigma2: 0.004937568  
##  
## Coefficients:  
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value  
## (Intercept) -0.233165 0.268621 -0.868006 -0.690237 0.3309 0.3936  
## scale(RC1meas) -0.036050 0.210424 -0.171322 -0.393324 0.4195 0.8653
```

```
## scale(logADmass) 0.090024 0.205212 0.438687 -0.357566 0.4777 0.6647
##
## R-squared: 0.01127 Adjusted R-squared: -0.06783
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7767579.
##
## sigma2: 0.004937568
## bootstrap mean: 0.004359243 (on raw scale)
## 0.003899474 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001531806,0.008186319)
##
## lambda: 0.7767579
## bootstrap mean: 0.627095 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modG4)
```

```
## [1] 28
```

```
### Cursorial
```

```
modG5 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFc, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 141 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, : the estimation
## You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
```

```
summary(modG5) #Table S13b
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NFc, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 74.88 -31.44
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -1.32359 -0.49147 0.01058 0.52753 1.48899
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.003163857
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.030344 0.213593 -0.142064 -0.441428 0.3558 0.88805
## scale(RC2ratios) 0.293784 0.134277 2.187889 0.034261 0.5444 0.03719
## PC1mass 0.443266 0.246179 1.800586 -0.036140 0.9215 0.08255
## PC2relegg 0.136088 0.135410 1.005005 -0.110783 0.4199 0.32350
##
## (Intercept)
```

```

## scale(RC2ratios) *
## PC1mass      .
## PC2relegg
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.2888    Adjusted R-squared:  0.2125
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.003163857
##      bootstrap mean: 0.002911271 (on raw scale)
##                   0.002814763 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001661574,0.004423858)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##      bootstrap mean: 0.01972668 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.3699143)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```

nobs(modG5)

```

```

## [1] 32

```

```

modPLG5 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFc, model = "lambda", boot = 100)

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 141 taxa with missing data
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, : the estimation of lambda
##                   You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".

```

```

summary(modPLG5) #Table S13b

```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = dat2NFc,
##         phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 74.88 -31.44
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -1.32359 -0.49147  0.01058  0.52753  1.48899
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.003163857
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.0097364  0.2159038 -0.0450959  -0.4411508    0.3378 0.96435
## RC2ratios    0.5944520  0.2717012  2.1878886   0.0394260    0.9899 0.03719 *
## PC1mass      0.4432664  0.2461789  1.8005864   0.0781012    0.8527 0.08255 .

```

```
## PC2relegg    0.1360879  0.1354102  1.0050051  -0.0781300    0.3458  0.32350
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.2888    Adjusted R-squared:  0.2125
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.003163857
##   bootstrap mean: 0.00274691 (on raw scale)
##                 0.002660658 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001652363,0.0042022)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##   bootstrap mean: 0.01252303 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.2758333)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modPLG5)
```

```
## [1] 32
```

```
visreg(modPLG5, xvar = "RC2ratios", band = FALSE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE, xlim=c(-2,4), ylim=c(-2,2))
```



```
modG6 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFc, model = "lar")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 141 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG6) #Table S13b
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),
```

```

##      data = dat2NFc, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
##      89.93 -39.97
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.5142 -0.8790 -0.2462  0.4200  3.0698
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9498764
## sigma2: 0.01214812
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)    0.331194  0.694859  0.476635   -0.934114    1.5694  0.6372
## scale(RC2ratios) -0.108039  0.190405 -0.567416   -0.396772    0.2496  0.5748
## scale(logADmass) -0.031572  0.153547 -0.205617   -0.382553    0.2238  0.8385
##
## R-squared: 0.01183   Adjusted R-squared: -0.05632
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9498764.
##
## sigma2: 0.01214812
##      bootstrap mean: 0.01012434 (on raw scale)
##                  0.00926877 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003103604,0.0189301)
##
## lambda: 0.9498764
##      bootstrap mean: 0.8655486 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
nobs(modG6)

## [1] 32
modG7 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFc, model = "lambda", boot = 100)

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 141 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, : the estimation of
## lambda may be biased. You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".

summary(modG7) #Table S13b

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NFc, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
##      77.85 -32.93
##

```

```

## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -1.43500 -0.43800 -0.00365  0.49403  1.19632
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.003471708
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)  -0.72210  0.48035 -1.50326   -1.50514    0.0906  0.14397
## scale(RC1meas) -0.46900  0.34210 -1.37095   -1.12733    0.1090  0.18128
## PC1mass       1.39382  0.62740  2.22159    0.37232    2.4833  0.03457 *
## PC2relegg     0.12549  0.14169  0.88572   -0.14465    0.3480  0.38331
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.2195      Adjusted R-squared: 0.1359
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.003471708
##      bootstrap mean: 0.002992777 (on raw scale)
##                   0.002880829 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001678101,0.004842287)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##      bootstrap mean: 0.01636279 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.214421)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modG7)
```

```
## [1] 32
```

```
modPLG7 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFc, model = "lambda"
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 141 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, : the estimation of lambda
## You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
```

```
summary(modPLG7) #Table S13
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = dat2NFc,
##        phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 77.85 -32.93
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max

```

```

## -1.43500 -0.43800 -0.00365 0.49403 1.19632
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.003471708
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.370678  0.277514 -1.335708  -0.739690    0.2009 0.19240
## RC1meas      -0.646045  0.471238 -1.370952  -1.559528    0.3585 0.18128
## PC1mass       1.393821  0.627398  2.221590   0.019627    2.3935 0.03457 *
## PC2relegg     0.125494  0.141686  0.885720  -0.144129    0.4003 0.38331
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.2195      Adjusted R-squared: 0.1359
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.003471708
##      bootstrap mean: 0.003232353 (on raw scale)
##                   0.003129557 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.0018701,0.004788661)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##      bootstrap mean: 0.02071879 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.3021262)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modPLG7)
```

```
## [1] 32
```

```
visreg(modPLG7, xvar = "RC1meas", band = FALSE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE, xlim=c(-2,2), ylim=
```



```
modG8 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFc, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 141 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG8) #Table S13
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass),
## data = dat2NFc, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 89.79 -39.89
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -1.6476 -1.0166 -0.2768 0.4926 3.1797
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9724515
## sigma2: 0.01287325
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) 0.35328 0.72283 0.48875 -0.93186 1.6811 0.6287
## scale(RC1meas) -0.11420 0.18745 -0.60925 -0.44805 0.2666 0.5471
## scale(logADmass) 0.01401 0.16479 0.08502 -0.32749 0.3019 0.9328
##
## R-squared: 0.01348 Adjusted R-squared: -0.05456
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9724515.
```

```
##
## sigma2: 0.01287325
##   bootstrap mean: 0.01029973 (on raw scale)
##                   0.009655463 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.004355755,0.01830597)
##
## lambda: 0.9724515
##   bootstrap mean: 0.8885022 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modG8)
```

```
## [1] 32
```

```
### Perching
```

```
modG9 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFp, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 114 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG9) #Table S13
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NFp, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 88.33 -38.17
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.44994  0.00202  0.42569  0.76170  1.55002
##
## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8242728
## sigma2: 0.004649494
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI
## (Intercept) -0.5582065  0.3045260 -1.8330341  -1.0981296   -0.0354
## scale(RC2ratios) 0.1956262  0.1120422  1.7460053  -0.0036654    0.4166
## PC1mass      0.2865373  0.1791913  1.5990581  -0.0991298    0.6359
## PC2relegg    -0.2097114  0.1284280 -1.6329103  -0.4070586    0.0690
##
##           p.value
## (Intercept) 0.07221 .
## scale(RC2ratios) 0.08639 .
## PC1mass      0.11554
## PC2relegg    0.10820
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.1677    Adjusted R-squared: 0.1224
```

```

##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8242728.
##
## sigma2: 0.004649494
##   bootstrap mean: 0.004146865 (on raw scale)
##                   0.0039076 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001978593,0.007355131)
##
## lambda: 0.8242728
##   bootstrap mean: 0.7352234 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
nobs(modG9)

## [1] 59
modPLG9 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFp, model ="lambda")

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 114 taxa with missing data
summary(modPLG9) #Table S13

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = dat2NFp,
##   phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 88.33 -38.17
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -1.44994  0.00202  0.42569  0.76170  1.55002
##
## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8242728
## sigma2: 0.004649494
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.517939  0.312813 -1.655748  -1.141475    0.0979  0.10347
## RC2ratios    0.364532  0.208781  1.746005  -0.017398    0.7722  0.08639
## PC1mass      0.286537  0.179191  1.599058  -0.047351    0.6180  0.11554
## PC2relegg   -0.209711  0.128428 -1.632910  -0.463776    0.0423  0.10820
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.1677   Adjusted R-squared: 0.1224
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8242728.
##
## sigma2: 0.004649494

```

```
## bootstrap mean: 0.003722319 (on raw scale)
## 0.003456441 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001640447,0.00708304)
##
## lambda: 0.8242728
## bootstrap mean: 0.6622123 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.9728158)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modPLG9)
```

```
## [1] 59
```

```
visreg(modPLG9, xvar = "RC2ratios", band = FALSE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE, xlim=c(-2,4), ylim=c(-2,2))
```



```
modG10 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFp, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 114 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG10) #Table S13
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),
## data = dat2NFp, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 93.74 -41.87
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.26088  0.04191  0.30756  0.63666  1.42976
##
```

```

## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1
## sigma2: 0.008625636
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)  -0.054747  0.374705 -0.146106  -0.719240    0.6613  0.8844
## scale(RC2ratios)  0.195266  0.123912  1.575842  -0.051283    0.4257  0.1207
## scale(logADmass)  0.036957  0.071314  0.518225  -0.073725    0.1787  0.6063
##
## R-squared: 0.04253   Adjusted R-squared: 0.008334
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1.
##
## sigma2: 0.008625636
##   bootstrap mean: 0.007042393 (on raw scale)
##                   0.006833964 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.00372479,0.009901294)
##
## lambda: 1
##   bootstrap mean: 0.9698831 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.842044,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modG10)
```

```
## [1] 59
```

```
modG11 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFp, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 114 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG11) #Table S13
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass),
## data = dat2NFp, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 93.01 -41.51
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.41252  0.09219  0.55949  0.89597  1.65518
##
## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8245465
## sigma2: 0.005209786
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value

```

```

## (Intercept)      -0.740106  0.273987 -2.701250   -1.237136   -0.2396  0.009123
## scale(RC1meas)   0.172247  0.136616  1.260810   -0.072688   0.3982  0.212605
## scale(logADmass) 0.061161  0.085403  0.716143   -0.097221   0.2050  0.476879
##
## (Intercept)      **
## scale(RC1meas)
## scale(logADmass)
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.06792   Adjusted R-squared: 0.03464
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8245465.
##
## sigma2: 0.005209786
##   bootstrap mean: 0.00486177 (on raw scale)
##                   0.004584133 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.002188519,0.008148372)
##
## lambda: 0.8245465
##   bootstrap mean: 0.7664249 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.2444866,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modG11)
```

```
## [1] 59
```

```
modPLG11 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFp, model ="lambda"
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 114 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modPLG11) #Table S13
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = dat2NFp,
##   phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 90.53 -39.26
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.37381  0.09754  0.60510  0.93775  1.72895
##
## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8826768
## sigma2: 0.005442581
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.82732  0.33079 -2.50105   -1.45530   -0.2336  0.01539 *

```

```

## RC1meas      -0.39980  0.41241 -0.96941   -0.99621      0.5068 0.33658
## PC1mass      0.63252  0.43263  1.46204   -0.37321      1.3682 0.14942
## PC2relegg   -0.28185  0.14066 -2.00377   -0.56682      0.0070 0.05003 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.1405    Adjusted R-squared:  0.09365
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8826768.
##
## sigma2: 0.005442581
##      bootstrap mean: 0.004551719 (on raw scale)
##                   0.004260811 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.00190974,0.008173456)
##
## lambda: 0.8826768
##      bootstrap mean: 0.7693759 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.9976591)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modPLG11)
```

```
## [1] 59
```

```
visreg(modPLG11, xvar = "RC1meas", band = FALSE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE, xlim=c(-2,2), ylim=c(-2,3))
```



```
modG12 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFp, model = "lar")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 114 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG12) #Table S13b
```

```
##
```

```

## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass),
## data = dat2NFp, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 96.13 -43.06
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.26199  0.07804  0.42144  0.69773  1.54087
##
## Mean tip height: 91.39389
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1
## sigma2: 0.008982045
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)   -0.154659   0.378286  -0.408841  -0.704747    0.5723  0.6842
## scale(RC1meas) -0.062177   0.154168  -0.403306  -0.377002    0.2590  0.6883
## scale(logADmass) 0.022055   0.082271   0.268083  -0.100023    0.1787  0.7896
##
## R-squared: 0.002967 Adjusted R-squared: -0.03264
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1.
##
## sigma2: 0.008982045
## bootstrap mean: 0.007801683 (on raw scale)
##                0.007617715 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.004695641,0.01059862)
##
## lambda: 1
## bootstrap mean: 0.9742391 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.8219841,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modG12)
```

```
## [1] 59
```

```
modPLG12 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ RC2ratios + logADmass, phy=PELVISphy1,data = dat2NFp, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ RC2ratios + logADmass, phy = PELVISphy1, data =
## dat2NFp, : will drop from the tree 114 taxa with missing data
```

```
visreg(modPLG12, xvar = "RC2ratios", points=list(cex=1.5), main = "P-AS x meas")
```

P-AS x meas


```
### Swimming
```

```
modG13 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFs, model =
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =
```

```
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 151 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG13) #Table S13b
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC2ratios) + PC1mass + PC2relegg,  
## data = dat2NFs, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
##
```

```
## AIC logLik
```

```
## 47.48 -17.74
```

```
##
```

```
## Raw residuals:
```

```
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max  
## -1.59747 -0.53874 -0.32700 -0.01346  1.13438
```

```
##
```

```
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
```

```
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
```

```
## lambda : 0.5555427
```

```
## sigma2: 0.003283613
```

```
##
```

```
## Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	StdErr	t.value	lowerbootCI	upperbootCI
(Intercept)	0.26876009	0.46784784	0.57446048	-0.57741841	1.1107
scale(RC2ratios)	0.27298186	0.19575798	1.39448648	-0.03559335	0.5969
PC1mass	0.86875295	0.35905045	2.41958464	0.20785396	1.4426
PC2relegg	0.00012556	0.16710506	0.00075137	-0.24353586	0.3358

```
##                p.value
## (Intercept)    0.57277
## scale(RC2ratios) 0.18014
## PC1mass        0.02634 *
## PC2relegg      0.99941
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.4301    Adjusted R-squared:  0.3351
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.5555427.
##
## sigma2: 0.003283613
##      bootstrap mean: 0.002422188 (on raw scale)
##                   0.00207807 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.0008536407,0.006692423)
##
## lambda: 0.5555427
##      bootstrap mean: 0.3103046 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.9520525)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modG13)
```

```
## [1] 22
```

```
modPLG13 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1,data = dat2NFs, model ="lambda
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC2ratios + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 151 taxa with missing data
```

```
visreg(modPLG13, xvar ="RC2ratios",overlay=TRUE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE, xlim=c(-2,4), ylim
```



```
modG14 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFs, model = "l
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass), phy =  
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 151 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG14) #Table S13
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC2ratios) + scale(logADmass),  
## data = dat2NFs, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)  
##  
## AIC logLik  
## 53.83 -21.91  
##  
## Raw residuals:  
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -1.86108 -0.96188 -0.68959 -0.02709 1.79957  
##  
## Mean tip height: 132.0409  
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:  
## lambda : 0.7246433  
## sigma2: 0.006234026  
##  
## Coefficients:  
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value  
## (Intercept) 0.27571 0.48910 0.56371 -0.78967 1.1291 0.5795  
## scale(RC2ratios) -0.29378 0.24657 -1.19144 -0.70919 0.1349 0.2482  
## scale(logADmass) 0.05659 0.18330 0.30872 -0.23555 0.4153 0.7609  
##  
## R-squared: 0.07727 Adjusted R-squared: -0.01986  
##  
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7246433.  
##  
## sigma2: 0.006234026  
## bootstrap mean: 0.004961048 (on raw scale)  
## 0.003944051 (on log scale, then back transformed)  
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001112814,0.01441335)  
##  
## lambda: 0.7246433  
## bootstrap mean: 0.4669434 (on raw scale)  
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.9702102)  
##  
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modG14)
```

```
## [1] 22
```

```
modG15 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFs, model = "l
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy =  
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 151 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG15) #Table S13
```

```
##
```

```

## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ scale(RC1meas) + PC1mass + PC2relegg,
## data = dat2NFs, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 48.65 -18.32
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -1.4379 -0.4610 -0.2236 0.2786 1.0619
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.3980268
## sigma2: 0.002926192
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.88742 0.92968 -0.95455 -2.59224 1.0219 0.35245
## scale(RC1meas) -0.44138 0.36708 -1.20240 -1.16205 0.2986 0.24479
## PC1mass 1.97263 0.81344 2.42504 0.28891 3.2763 0.02605 *
## PC2relegg -0.12999 0.15812 -0.82206 -0.48860 0.2196 0.42180
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.4118 Adjusted R-squared: 0.3137
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.3980268.
##
## sigma2: 0.002926192
## bootstrap mean: 0.00217876 (on raw scale)
## 0.001927846 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.0008946909,0.005198881)
##
## lambda: 0.3980268
## bootstrap mean: 0.1436629 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.858523)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modG15)
```

```
## [1] 22
```

```
modPLG15 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas +PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFs, model ="lambda
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = PELVISphy1, :
## will drop from the tree 151 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modPLG15) #Table S13
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ RC1meas + PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = dat2NFs,
## phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##

```

```

##      AIC logLik
## 48.65 -18.32
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.4379 -0.4610 -0.2236  0.2786  1.0619
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.3980268
## sigma2: 0.002926192
##
## Coefficients:
##      Estimate  StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.37724  0.58684 -0.64284   -1.57475    0.8120  0.52844
## RC1meas      -0.86267  0.71745 -1.20240   -2.14927    0.3619  0.24479
## PC1mass       1.97263  0.81344  2.42504    0.36771    3.5570  0.02605 *
## PC2relegg    -0.12999  0.15812 -0.82206   -0.35223    0.1100  0.42180
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.4118      Adjusted R-squared: 0.3137
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.3980268.
##
## sigma2: 0.002926192
##      bootstrap mean: 0.002111247 (on raw scale)
##                      0.001783912 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.0007519285,0.005965244)
##
## lambda: 0.3980268
##      bootstrap mean: 0.1250472 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.8081513)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modPLG15)
```

```
## [1] 22
```

```
visreg(modPLG15, xvar = "RC1meas", overlay=TRUE, points=list(cex=1.5), legend=TRUE, xlim=c(-2,2), ylim=c
```



```
modG16 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy=PELVISphy1, data = dat2NFs, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass), phy =
## PELVISphy1, : will drop from the tree 151 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modG16) #Table S13
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ scale(RC1meas) + scale(logADmass),
## data = dat2NFs, phy = PELVISphy1, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 53.16 -21.58
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -2.19776 -1.02491 -0.74219 -0.08952  1.52083
##
## Mean tip height: 132.0409
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.6852362
## sigma2: 0.005628127
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)    0.318194  0.460416  0.691100  -0.429917    1.0385  0.4979
## scale(RC1meas)  0.554100  0.379987  1.458206  -0.041135    1.2259  0.1611
## scale(logADmass) -0.505428  0.335272 -1.507515  -1.049004   -0.0005  0.1481
##
## R-squared: 0.1094    Adjusted R-squared: 0.01567
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.6852362.
```

```
##
## sigma2: 0.005628127
##   bootstrap mean: 0.004301641 (on raw scale)
##                   0.003487938 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001257387,0.0112305)
##
## lambda: 0.6852362
##   bootstrap mean: 0.4175623 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.9858953)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modG16)
```

```
## [1] 22
```

9 DEVELOPMENTAL MODES: testing for effects on egg shape

Table S8

```
##ELONGATION
```

```
modH1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +devel +LOCO +sCSegg +IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = N
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + devel + LOCO + : will
## drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + devel + LOCO + : 5
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modH1) #Table S8
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + devel +
##   LOCO + sCSegg + IncSite, data = NEOphydat, phy = NEOphy,
##   model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 1705.6 -834.8
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -3.0138 -0.3053  0.2811  0.7704  4.0439
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.777189
## sigma2: 0.007669818
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI    p.value
## (Intercept) -0.6377039  0.3779494 -1.6872733  -1.3287052    0.0967 0.0918954
## sPC1mass     0.3926710  0.0551353  7.1219468   0.3084228    0.4950 2.169e-12
## sPC2relegg   0.0049316  0.0340471  0.1448452  -0.0441974    0.0584 0.8848654
## sHWI         0.1703188  0.0468308  3.6368942   0.0953137    0.2698 0.0002915
## develP      -0.0895528  0.2134444 -0.4195603  -0.4160130    0.3108 0.6749063
```

```

## LOCOC      0.0558166  0.1883824  0.2962940  -0.2587656    0.3713  0.7670736
## LOCOF     -1.1273195  0.6035909 -1.8676881  -2.0732235   -0.0794  0.0621286
## LOCOP     -0.0579101  0.2283353 -0.2536185  -0.4957629    0.3411  0.7998479
## LOCOS      1.0282420  0.2227259  4.6166248   0.5548571    1.4260  4.464e-06
## sCSeegg   -0.1759935  0.0370761 -4.7468122  -0.2389315   -0.1076  2.401e-06
## IncSiteCU  0.4264905  0.1702617  2.5049112   0.1239639    0.7262  0.0124230
## IncSiteCV  0.0313401  0.1552405  0.2018813  -0.2002107    0.2915  0.8400549
## IncSiteDO  0.5567121  0.1888128  2.9484876   0.2205382    0.8500  0.0032754
## IncSiteMO  2.2534492  0.5358837  4.2051088   1.3047990    3.2118  2.869e-05
## IncSitePL  0.4684994  0.1669350  2.8064779   0.1980132    0.8936  0.0051162
## IncSiteSC  0.2152348  0.1886282  1.1410533  -0.0953390    0.6178  0.2541496

```

```

##
## (Intercept) .
## sPC1mass    ***
## sPC2relegg
## sHWI        ***
## develP
## LOCOC
## LOCOF      .
## LOCOP
## LOCOS      ***
## sCSeegg    ***
## IncSiteCU  *
## IncSiteCV
## IncSiteDO  **
## IncSiteMO  ***
## IncSitePL  **
## IncSiteSC
## ---

```

```

## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##

```

```

## R-squared:  0.1752    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1615
##

```

```

## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.777189.
##

```

```

## sigma2: 0.007669818
##      bootstrap mean: 0.007277542 (on raw scale)
##                  0.007248921 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.00595235,0.008451008)
##

```

```

## lambda: 0.777189
##      bootstrap mean: 0.7530925 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6619037,0.8204038)
##

```

```

## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```

###ASYMMETRY
modH2 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +devel +LOCO +sCSeegg +IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = NI

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + devel + LOCO + : will
## drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + devel + LOCO + : 5
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored

```

summary(modH2) #Table S8

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + devel +
##       LOCO + sCSeegg + IncSite, data = NEOphydat, phy = NEOphy,
##       model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##       AIC logLik
## 1678.8 -821.4
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.9634  0.0243  0.7158  1.3009  4.0989
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.7972499
## sigma2: 0.007774615
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept) -0.967522  0.383235 -2.524619  -1.793629  -0.4714  0.0117523 *
## sPC1mass     0.099074  0.054760  1.809246   0.011475   0.2081  0.0707446 .
## sPC2relegg  -0.025591  0.033560 -0.762543  -0.084054   0.0315  0.4459345
## sHWI         0.238815  0.046474  5.138669   0.157346   0.3498  3.39e-07 ***
## develP      0.059767  0.215191  0.277737  -0.271342   0.4505  0.7812774
## LOCO        0.144460  0.189497  0.762334  -0.227454   0.5092  0.4460593
## LOCOF       1.269862  0.612419  2.073519   0.235504   2.4144  0.0384064 *
## LOCOPL      0.031118  0.230325  0.135106  -0.383178   0.4902  0.8925581
## LOCOS       0.139372  0.223691  0.623055  -0.325237   0.5043  0.5334055
## sCSeegg     0.129962  0.036660  3.545093   0.047179   0.1955  0.0004126 ***
## IncSiteCU   0.298097  0.169513  1.758545   0.032377   0.6776  0.0789928 .
## IncSiteCV   0.244258  0.153443  1.591841  -0.010833   0.5558  0.1117696
## IncSiteDO   0.320572  0.187693  1.707957   0.053154   0.7573  0.0879872 .
## IncSiteMO  -0.440835  0.542548 -0.812526  -1.391019   0.9218  0.4167036
## IncSitePL   0.073048  0.166344  0.439140  -0.226619   0.3996  0.6606651
## IncSiteSC   0.526214  0.187662  2.804057   0.185390   0.8999  0.0051544 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.08188   Adjusted R-squared: 0.06666
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7972499.
##
## sigma2: 0.007774615
##       bootstrap mean: 0.007331818 (on raw scale)
##                   0.007301785 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##       bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006136132,0.008588715)
##
## lambda: 0.7972499
##       bootstrap mean: 0.774247 (on raw scale)
##       bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6936887,0.8479822)
##
```

```
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

10 GLOBAL MODELS: all species, including paleognaths

Supplementary Material Table S6

```
#Elongation
```

```
modJ1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSegg +IncSite, phy=ALLphy1, data = ALLphydat, mo
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg + IncSite, :  
## will drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg + IncSite, : 5  
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modJ1) #Table S6
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg +  
## IncSite, data = ALLphydat, phy = ALLphy1, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)  
##  
## AIC logLik  
## 1769.6 -871.8  
##  
## Raw residuals:  
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -3.2129 -0.4068 0.1478 0.6093 3.9219  
##  
## Mean tip height: 108.1962  
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:  
## lambda : 0.8264946  
## sigma2: 0.008714259  
##  
## Coefficients:  
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value  
## (Intercept) -0.194888 0.349605 -0.557451 -0.898721 0.4823 0.577354  
## sPC1mass 0.445581 0.054824 8.127442 0.331493 0.5466 1.399e-15 ***  
## sPC2relegg 0.029972 0.033459 0.895771 -0.025138 0.0863 0.370608  
## sHWI 0.178312 0.044972 3.965005 0.081635 0.2658 7.906e-05 ***  
## sCSegg -0.161242 0.034434 -4.682585 -0.222081 -0.0806 3.257e-06 ***  
## IncSiteCU 0.202861 0.170975 1.186496 -0.122800 0.5477 0.235731  
## IncSiteCV -0.157063 0.154308 -1.017855 -0.417183 0.1392 0.309013  
## IncSiteDO 0.352587 0.191043 1.845584 0.052340 0.7388 0.065272 .  
## IncSiteMO 1.733639 0.564722 3.069897 0.659808 2.6498 0.002204 **  
## IncSitePL 0.169925 0.163469 1.039497 -0.096290 0.4856 0.298845  
## IncSiteSC -0.117789 0.176471 -0.667469 -0.452430 0.1827 0.504639  
## ---  
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1  
##  
## R-squared: 0.1404 Adjusted R-squared: 0.1311  
##  
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8264946.  
##
```

```
## sigma2: 0.008714259
##   bootstrap mean: 0.008404225 (on raw scale)
##                   0.008374012 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.007239806,0.009881833)
##
## lambda: 0.8264946
##   bootstrap mean: 0.8158915 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7590839,0.866196)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modJ1)
```

```
## [1] 936
```

```
#Asymmetry
```

```
modJ2 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSeg +IncSite, phy=ALLphy1, data = ALLphydat, mo
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg + IncSite, :
## will drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg + IncSite, : 5
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modJ2) #Table S6
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg +
##   IncSite, data = ALLphydat, phy = ALLphy1, model = "lambda",
##   boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 1711.4 -842.7
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.5456  0.2525  0.9587  1.5215  4.5191
##
## Mean tip height: 108.1962
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8144593
## sigma2: 0.0079541
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI    p.value
## (Intercept) -1.0415593  0.3326276 -3.1313071  -1.7478511   -0.2742  0.001795
## sPC1mass     0.0939261  0.0528470  1.7773217   0.0111975    0.2040  0.075844
## sPC2relegg  -0.0191239  0.0324257 -0.5897762  -0.0851380    0.0441  0.555485
## sHWI         0.2328326  0.0433352  5.3728289   0.1570827    0.3169  9.812e-08
## sCSeg        0.0909637  0.0332823  2.7330928   0.0267362    0.1489  0.006394
## IncSiteCU    0.2192212  0.1646027  1.3318205  -0.1015923    0.5876  0.183247
## IncSiteCV    0.1819006  0.1493261  1.2181431  -0.1121300    0.4626  0.223480
## IncSiteD0    0.2429082  0.1841472  1.3190980  -0.1170776    0.6029  0.187463
## IncSiteM0   -0.5322525  0.5376181 -0.9900197  -1.5916288    0.5397  0.322423
## IncSitePL    0.0051893  0.1572479  0.0330010  -0.3135321    0.3204  0.973681
## IncSiteSC    0.3834287  0.1698526  2.2574200   0.0374997    0.7218  0.024214
```

```

##
## (Intercept) **
## sPC1mass .
## sPC2relegg
## sHWI ***
## sCSeegg **
## IncSiteCU
## IncSiteCV
## IncSiteDO
## IncSiteMO
## IncSitePL
## IncSiteSC *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.06391   Adjusted R-squared:  0.05379
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8144593.
##
## sigma2: 0.0079541
##   bootstrap mean: 0.007651317 (on raw scale)
##                   0.00761682 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006519327,0.00901806)
##
## lambda: 0.8144593
##   bootstrap mean: 0.801248 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7317524,0.8591014)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modJ2)
```

```
## [1] 936
```

```
(nfams <- ALLphydat %>% group_by(Family) %>% summarise(number = n()))
```

```

## # A tibble: 193 x 2
##   Family          number
##   <fct>          <int>
## 1 Acanthisittidae     1
## 2 Acanthizidae       4
## 3 Accipitridae      25
## 4 Acrocephalidae    10
## 5 Aegithalidae       2
## 6 Aegithinidae       1
## 7 Aegothelidae       1
## 8 Alaudidae          13
## 9 Alcedinidae       18
## 10 Alcidae           14
## # ... with 183 more rows

```

11 GLOBAL MODELS: paleognaths only

Table S19; Figure 4b

```
modK1<- phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg +sCSegg, phy=PALEOphy, data = PALEOphydat, model = "lambda",
summary(modK1) #Figure 4b, Table S19
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSegg, data = PALEOphydat,
## phy = PALEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 45.10 -16.55
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -1.7287 -0.1505 0.4462 0.8958 1.4485
##
## Mean tip height: 76.99147
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.9407445
## sigma2: 0.0111165
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.445538 0.861566 -0.517127 -1.724476 1.1682 0.61531
## PC1mass 0.446617 0.514491 0.868075 -0.276694 1.2782 0.40389
## PC2relegg 0.420962 0.193399 2.176651 0.097261 0.7262 0.05217
## sCSegg -0.077425 0.105869 -0.731331 -0.247511 0.0887 0.47987
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.3663 Adjusted R-squared: 0.1934
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.9407445.
##
## sigma2: 0.0111165
## bootstrap mean: 0.006782629 (on raw scale)
## 0.005649294 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001508887,0.0160754)
##
## lambda: 0.9407445
## bootstrap mean: 0.561911 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
modK1a<- lm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg, data = PALEOphydat) #Table S19 Figure 4b
summary(modK1a)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = PALEOphydat)
##
## Residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -2.04454 -0.26813 0.05253 0.66193 1.04585
```

```
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.9431     0.5732  -1.646  0.1258
## PC1mass      0.8425     0.3020   2.790  0.0163 *
## PC2relegg    0.5382     0.1807   2.978  0.0115 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 0.9539 on 12 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.4786, Adjusted R-squared:  0.3917
## F-statistic: 5.508 on 2 and 12 DF,  p-value: 0.02009
```

```
visreg(modK1a, xvar = "PC2relegg", gg=TRUE, line=list(col="red"),
        points=list(size=4, pch=18), jitter=2) #Figure 4b
```



```
modK1b <- lm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, subset(PALEOphydat, Order == "Tinamiformes")) #Table S19 Figure
summary(modK1b)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = subset(PALEOphydat,
##   Order == "Tinamiformes"))
##
## Residuals:
## Crypturellus_cinnamomeus      Crypturellus_soui      Eudromia_elegans
##           -1.461782           -0.069164           0.817671
## Nothocercus_bonapartei      Nothura_maculosa      Rhynchotus_rufescens
```

```
##           0.510113           0.614042           0.000159
##           Tinamus_tao
##           -0.411041
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.8597     0.9294  -0.925   0.407
## PC1mass      0.7339     1.0902   0.673   0.538
## PC2relegg    0.3197     0.5327   0.600   0.581
##
## Residual standard error: 0.9508 on 4 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1875, Adjusted R-squared:  -0.2187
## F-statistic: 0.4617 on 2 and 4 DF,  p-value: 0.6601
```

```
plot_model(modK1b, type = "pred", show.data=TRUE)
```

```
## $PC1mass
```

Predicted values of RC2EL


```
##
## $PC2relegg
```

Predicted values of RC2EL


```
ggplot(PALEOphydat, aes(x = PC2relegg, y = RC2EL)) +  
  theme_bw() +  
  geom_point(color="coral", size=2) +  
  geom_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, linetype="solid",  
             color="coral", size=1, na.rm = TRUE) +  
  theme(legend.position = "none") #Figure 4b
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


12 GLOBAL MODELS: Neognaths

12.1 All Neognaths

Tables 1 and S5, Figures 2a,b, S1

```
plotTree(NEOphy,type="fan",fsize=0.2,lwd=1, ftype="i")
```


neognaths-1.pdf neognaths-1.bb

```
(nfams <- NEOphydat %>% group_by(Family) %>% summarise(number = n()))
```

```
## # A tibble: 188 x 2
##   Family      number
##   <fct>      <int>
## 1 Acanthisittidae      1
## 2 Acanthizidae        4
## 3 Accipitridae       25
## 4 Acrocephalidae     10
## 5 Aegithalidae        2
## 6 Aegithinidae        1
## 7 Aegothelidae        1
## 8 Alaudidae          13
## 9 Alcedinidae        18
## 10 Alcidae           14
## # ... with 178 more rows
```

```
(nords <- NEOphydat %>% group_by(Order) %>% summarise(number = n()))
```

```
## # A tibble: 34 x 2
##   Order      number
##   <fct>      <int>
## 1 Accipitriformes    31
## 2 Anseriformes      47
## 3 Apodiformes       25
## 4 Bucerotiformes     3
## 5 Caprimulgiformes  14
## 6 Cariamiformes      1
## 7 Charadriiformes  111
```

```
## 8 Ciconiiformes      3
## 9 Coliiformes       1
## 10 Columbiformes    11
## # ... with 24 more rows
```

```
#Elongation
```

```
modL1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSegg +IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = NEOphydat, model="lambda", boot=100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg + IncSite, :
## will drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg + IncSite, : 5
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modL1) #Table S5 and Figure 2a,b
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg +
##       IncSite, data = NEOphydat, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##       boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 1725.3 -849.7
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -3.1465 -0.3339  0.2262  0.6834  3.9737
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8101881
## sigma2: 0.008509305
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI    p.value
## (Intercept) -0.3257768  0.3502643 -0.9300884  -0.8685936    0.4479  0.35257
## sPC1mass     0.4340085  0.0555398  7.8143731   0.3383633    0.5361 1.521e-14
## sPC2relegg   0.0089356  0.0340596  0.2623502  -0.0527849    0.0736  0.79311
## sHWI         0.1823889  0.0451705  4.0377894   0.0924864    0.2594 5.850e-05
## sCSegg      -0.1696491  0.0375659 -4.5160444  -0.2358999   -0.1159 7.129e-06
## IncSiteCU    0.2427818  0.1706085  1.4230348  -0.1139838    0.6333  0.15507
## IncSiteCV   -0.1232749  0.1543299 -0.7987752  -0.4488434    0.1748  0.42463
## IncSiteDO    0.3915277  0.1903868  2.0564858  -0.0110555    0.7372  0.04002
## IncSiteMO    1.8404174  0.5584619  3.2955112   0.7779430    2.6847  0.00102
## IncSitePL    0.2153185  0.1637330  1.3150584  -0.1683750    0.5182  0.18882
## IncSiteSC   -0.0411894  0.1805923 -0.2280796  -0.4402157    0.2633  0.81964
##
## (Intercept)
## sPC1mass     ***
## sPC2relegg
## sHWI         ***
## sCSegg      ***
## IncSiteCU
## IncSiteCV
## IncSiteDO   *
```

```

## IncSiteMO **
## IncSitePL
## IncSiteSC
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.1434    Adjusted R-squared:  0.134
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8101881.
##
## sigma2: 0.008509305
##      bootstrap mean: 0.008308681 (on raw scale)
##                   0.008274429 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006838231,0.009771201)
##
## lambda: 0.8101881
##      bootstrap mean: 0.8029088 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7344759,0.8611611)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```

nobs(modL1)

```

```

## [1] 921

```

```

#same but controlling for LOCO x HWI
modL2 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI *LOCO +sCSegg +IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = NEOphydat

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI * LOCO + sCSegg + : will
## drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI * LOCO + sCSegg + : 5
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored

```

```

summary(modL2) #Table 1

```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI * LOCO +
##       sCSegg + IncSite, data = NEOphydat, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##       boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 1707.2 -832.6
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -2.9741 -0.3152  0.2857  0.7670  4.0502
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.775388
## sigma2: 0.007605548
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI    p.value
## (Intercept) -0.7433919  0.3822139 -1.9449628  -1.4414255   -0.0665  0.052090

```

```

## sPC1mass      0.3999943  0.0551424  7.2538452   0.2848745    0.4844 8.722e-13
## sPC2relegg    0.0027587  0.0340009  0.0811358  -0.0694487    0.0689 0.935352
## sHWI          0.2492822  0.1173286  2.1246507   0.0315992    0.4916 0.033887
## LOCOC         0.1399389  0.2340934  0.5977907  -0.3571567    0.6422 0.550130
## LOCOF        -1.0158715  3.1445179 -0.3230611  -6.7907179    5.2941 0.746724
## LOCOP         0.0047969  0.2481688  0.0193292  -0.5530514    0.4380 0.984583
## LOCOS         1.2769810  0.3032320  4.2112338   0.7389939    1.8798 2.795e-05
## sCSeegg      -0.1752202  0.0372610 -4.7025079  -0.2207811   -0.1065 2.972e-06
## IncSiteCU     0.4079082  0.1705671  2.3914818   0.0816531    0.7547 0.016985
## IncSiteCV     0.0218917  0.1551378  0.1411111  -0.2368475    0.2705 0.887814
## IncSiteDO     0.5267752  0.1891237  2.7853470   0.0979926    0.8222 0.005459
## IncSiteMO     2.2165287  0.5326423  4.1613832   1.2455959    3.2247 3.466e-05
## IncSitePL     0.4379955  0.1666034  2.6289704   0.1522542    0.7375 0.008710
## IncSiteSC     0.1691452  0.1857336  0.9106872  -0.1544298    0.5741 0.362703
## sHWI:LOCOC    0.0296643  0.1429411  0.2075284  -0.3083956    0.3153 0.835644
## sHWI:LOCOF   -0.0845567  1.8800718 -0.0449753  -3.4444123    3.6921 0.964137
## sHWI:LOCOP   -0.1331607  0.1350647 -0.9859024  -0.3901706    0.0885 0.324445
## sHWI:LOCOS   -0.2754126  0.1975900 -1.3938587  -0.6018155    0.0615 0.163704
##
## (Intercept) .
## sPC1mass      ***
## sPC2relegg
## sHWI          *
## LOCOC
## LOCOF
## LOCOP
## LOCOS        ***
## sCSeegg      ***
## IncSiteCU     *
## IncSiteCV
## IncSiteDO     **
## IncSiteMO     ***
## IncSitePL     **
## IncSiteSC
## sHWI:LOCOC
## sHWI:LOCOF
## sHWI:LOCOP
## sHWI:LOCOS
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.1793    Adjusted R-squared: 0.163
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.775388.
##
## sigma2: 0.007605548
##      bootstrap mean: 0.007239424 (on raw scale)
##                  0.007204105 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.00578244,0.008479184)
##
## lambda: 0.775388
##      bootstrap mean: 0.7599316 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6737363,0.8226551)
##

```

```
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modL2)
```

```
## [1] 921
```

```
#Asymmetry
```

```
modL3 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg + IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = NEOphydat, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg + IncSite, :  
## will drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg + IncSite, : 5  
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modL3) #Table S5 and Fig 1a,b
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg +  
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)
```

```
##
```

```
## AIC logLik
```

```
## 1673.5 -823.8
```

```
##
```

```
## Raw residuals:
```

```
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -1.8627 0.0157 0.6961 1.2733 4.1632
```

```
##
```

```
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
```

```
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
```

```
## lambda : 0.8033366
```

```
## sigma2: 0.007920367
```

```
##
```

```
## Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	StdErr	t.value	lowerbootCI	upperbootCI	p.value	
## (Intercept)	-0.842478	0.337038	-2.499650	-1.411137	-0.2325	0.0126067	*
## sPC1mass	0.108736	0.053847	2.019350	0.027318	0.2188	0.0437436	*
## sPC2relegg	-0.029422	0.033113	-0.888529	-0.078945	0.0384	0.3744908	
## sHWI	0.217022	0.043778	4.957326	0.139768	0.3087	8.523e-07	***
## sCSegeg	0.132385	0.036485	3.628496	0.048652	0.1983	0.0003009	***
## IncSiteCU	0.279881	0.165258	1.693598	-0.057804	0.5471	0.0906838	.
## IncSiteCV	0.230397	0.149896	1.537045	-0.010082	0.5031	0.1246300	
## IncSiteD0	0.299848	0.184535	1.624889	0.013074	0.6061	0.1045325	
## IncSiteM0	-0.411979	0.537685	-0.766208	-1.512547	0.6248	0.4437513	
## IncSitePL	0.069482	0.158528	0.438296	-0.180168	0.2766	0.6612760	
## IncSiteSC	0.543514	0.174910	3.107389	0.232665	0.8977	0.0019461	**

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
##
```

```
## R-squared: 0.07677 Adjusted R-squared: 0.06662
```

```
##
```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8033366.
```

```
##
```

```
## sigma2: 0.007920367
```

```
## bootstrap mean: 0.007781014 (on raw scale)
```

```

##          0.007753654 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##    bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006608326,0.008928347)
##
## lambda: 0.8033366
##    bootstrap mean: 0.7980979 (on raw scale)
##    bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7334357,0.8563159)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
#same but controlling for LOCO x HWI interaction
modL4 <- phyloilm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +LOCO*sHWI +sCSegg +IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = NEOphydat

## Warning in phyloilm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + LOCO * sHWI + sCSegg + : will
## drop from the tree 10 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phyloilm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + LOCO * sHWI + sCSegg + : 5
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored

summary(modL4) #Table 1

##
## Call:
## phyloilm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + LOCO * sHWI +
##   sCSegg + IncSite, data = NEOphydat, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##   boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 1675.7 -816.8
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -2.2652  0.0217  0.6878  1.2727  4.2209
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.799218
## sigma2: 0.007731015
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI   p.value
## (Intercept) -0.650557  0.387345 -1.679531  -1.270874    0.1158  0.0933949 .
## sPC1mass     0.095130  0.054694  1.739322  -0.010253    0.2163  0.0823193 .
## sPC2relegg  -0.027003  0.033433 -0.807657  -0.092574    0.0389  0.4195010
## LOCOC       -0.170373  0.234696 -0.725932  -0.605552    0.1872  0.4680690
## LOCOCF      -1.636391  3.070346 -0.532966  -8.296009    3.4429  0.5941882
## LOCOP       -0.264379  0.249808 -1.058327  -0.711264    0.1964  0.2901896
## LOCOS       -0.172583  0.302306 -0.570890  -0.758412    0.2997  0.5682165
## sHWI         0.013538  0.116321  0.116389  -0.191596    0.2338  0.9073703
## sCSegg       0.125887  0.036765  3.424140   0.062345    0.1851  0.0006445 ***
## IncSiteCU    0.326474  0.169705  1.923769  -0.029401    0.6335  0.0546979 .
## IncSiteCV    0.265044  0.153050  1.731748  -0.013397    0.5708  0.0836603 .
## IncSiteDO    0.332966  0.187798  1.772999  -0.018616    0.6519  0.0765663 .
## IncSiteMO   -0.415715  0.540642 -0.768929  -1.399372    0.5514  0.4421367
## IncSitePL    0.104071  0.166001  0.626928  -0.192617    0.4413  0.5308651
## IncSiteSC    0.480227  0.184707  2.599944   0.168476    0.8623  0.0094763 **
## LOCOC:sHWI  0.397416  0.141746  2.803721   0.123565    0.6471  0.0051601 **

```

```

## LOCOP:sHWI -1.350692 1.833377 -0.736723 -4.978134 1.4973 0.4614822
## LOCOP:sHWI 0.198667 0.133833 1.484438 -0.018697 0.4406 0.1380421
## LOCOS:sHWI 0.214182 0.194986 1.098448 -0.081138 0.5112 0.2723019
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.09083 Adjusted R-squared: 0.07269
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.799218.
##
## sigma2: 0.007731015
## bootstrap mean: 0.007269277 (on raw scale)
## 0.007238416 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006065413,0.008629302)
##
## lambda: 0.799218
## bootstrap mean: 0.7804182 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7128576,0.8411077)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modL4)
```

```
## [1] 921
```

12.2 Neognaths without Trochilidae and Megapodiidae

Table S7

```
NEOphydat2 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(!Family %in% c("Trochilidae", "Megapodiidae"))
#Elongation
```

```
modM1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSegg , phy=NEOphy, data = NEOphydat2, model = "lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg, phy =
## NEOphy, : will drop from the tree 42 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg, phy =
## NEOphy, : 5 taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modM1) #Table S7
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg,
## data = NEOphydat2, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 1644.7 -815.3
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -3.1906 -0.2904 0.2975 0.7344 2.6355
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.7991821
## sigma2: 0.008206339

```

```

##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI    p.value
## (Intercept) -0.2344102  0.3144831 -0.7453825  -0.8218596    0.4637 0.4562387
## sPC1mass     0.4614822  0.0544178  8.4803597   0.3690017    0.5818 < 2.2e-16
## sPC2relegg   0.0078821  0.0339853  0.2319281  -0.0522665    0.0768 0.8166476
## sHWI         0.1535970  0.0442710  3.4694731   0.0606439    0.2251 0.0005467
## sCSegg      -0.1604442  0.0372370 -4.3087343  -0.2173399   -0.0744 1.826e-05
##
## (Intercept)
## sPC1mass     ***
## sPC2relegg
## sHWI         ***
## sCSegg      ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.1282    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1242
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7991821.
##
## sigma2: 0.008206339
##      bootstrap mean: 0.00805297 (on raw scale)
##                   0.008025979 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006798622,0.009379729)
##
## lambda: 0.7991821
##      bootstrap mean: 0.7924619 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.723672,0.8535908)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modM1)
```

```
## [1] 889
```

```
#Asymmetry
```

```
modM2 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSegg, phy = NEOphy, subset(NEOphydat, !Family %in%
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg, phy =
## NEOphy, : will drop from the tree 42 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg, phy =
## NEOphy, : 5 taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modM2) #Table S7
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg,
## data = subset(NEOphydat, !Family %in% c("Trochilidae", "Megapodiidae")),
## phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
##      1636   -811
##
## Raw residuals:

```

```

##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.6445 -0.0408  0.7224  1.2809  4.4619
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.804265
## sigma2: 0.008218152
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI   p.value
## (Intercept) -0.600874  0.315612 -1.903839   -1.242324   -0.0354  0.0572556 .
## sPC1mass     0.081125  0.054266  1.494943   -0.037823    0.1719  0.1352863
## sPC2relegg  -0.032211  0.033824 -0.952321   -0.088665    0.0136  0.3411944
## sHWI         0.244242  0.044161  5.530768    0.152327    0.3476  4.199e-08 ***
## sCSeg       0.123722  0.037083  3.336335    0.048821    0.1873  0.0008843 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.05726   Adjusted R-squared: 0.05299
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.804265.
##
## sigma2: 0.008218152
##      bootstrap mean: 0.008092423 (on raw scale)
##                   0.008062164 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006818268,0.009620275)
##
## lambda: 0.804265
##      bootstrap mean: 0.7998081 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7290468,0.8555066)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

13 WITHIN-TAXON ANALYSES

13.1 Within orders

Tables S18, S22; Figures 7, S7

```

#all neognaths
#mean relative egg size across the neognaths
MeanCI(NEOphydat$PC2relegg, na.rm = TRUE) #mean is -0.005

```

```

##           mean      lwr.ci      upr.ci
## -0.004627979 -0.068181290  0.058925332

```

```

##Accipitriiformes
NEOphydat1 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Accipitriiformes") %>% droplevels()
modP1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg +sCSeg +sHWI +IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat1, mo

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSeg + sHWI + IncSite, : will
## drop from the tree 900 taxa with missing data

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSeg + sHWI + IncSite, : the estimation of lambda
##                               You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".

```

```
summary(modP1) #Table S18, Figure 3
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI +
##       IncSite, data = NEOphydat1, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##       boot = 100)
##
##       AIC logLik
## 57.06 -20.53
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.3411 -0.2374  0.0424  0.2644  1.0335
##
## Mean tip height: 79.19371
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.002780115
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI   p.value
## (Intercept) -1.065795  0.269628 -3.952839  -1.428358  -0.6278  0.0005592 ***
## PC1mass      0.039558  0.329346  0.120112  -0.528919   0.6533  0.9053546
## PC2relegg    0.028049  0.119794  0.234146  -0.147386   0.2774  0.8167788
## sCSegg      -0.250923  0.329485 -0.761562  -0.855728   0.3663  0.4534460
## sHWI        -0.019314  0.246906 -0.078225  -0.364294   0.3914  0.9382718
## IncSiteSC   2.051692  0.335566  6.114126   1.533233   2.6007  2.166e-06 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.7153    Adjusted R-squared: 0.6584
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.002780115
##       bootstrap mean: 0.002368077 (on raw scale)
##                   0.002217273 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##       bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001284947,0.005060879)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##       bootstrap mean: 0.03483587 (on raw scale)
##       bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.7535554)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
NEOphydat1 %>% drop_na(PC2relegg) %>% summarize(mean = mean(PC2relegg)) #Figure S2
```

```
##           mean
## 1 -0.2753922
```

```
###Charadriiformes
```

```
NEOphydat2 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Charadriiformes") %>% droplevels()
```

```
#Elongation
```

```
modP2 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sCSegg +sHWI +IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat2, n
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI + IncSite, :  
## will drop from the tree 821 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modP2) #Table 18a, Figure 3
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI +  
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat2, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)  
##  
## AIC logLik  
## 169.07 -75.53  
##  
## Raw residuals:  
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -1.24768 -0.20818 0.01759 0.26143 1.43199  
##  
## Mean tip height: 59.8139  
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:  
## lambda : 0.5288375  
## sigma2: 0.00546824  
##  
## Coefficients:  
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value  
## (Intercept) -0.121108 0.298309 -0.405981 -0.728486 0.4728 0.685599  
## sPC1mass 0.698250 0.129685 5.384214 0.498854 0.9568 4.605e-07 ***  
## sPC2relegg 0.271218 0.090040 3.012190 0.065233 0.4118 0.003264 **  
## sCSegg 0.079039 0.179212 0.441037 -0.323849 0.3659 0.660111  
## sHWI 0.011999 0.133273 0.090034 -0.266930 0.2716 0.928435  
## IncSitePL -0.355754 0.260042 -1.368063 -0.743561 0.1382 0.174269  
## IncSiteSC -0.335086 0.247531 -1.353711 -0.823339 0.0876 0.178792  
## ---  
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1  
##  
## R-squared: 0.3064 Adjusted R-squared: 0.266  
##  
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.5288375.  
##  
## sigma2: 0.00546824  
## bootstrap mean: 0.004448176 (on raw scale)  
## 0.004313506 (on log scale, then back transformed)  
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.00288183,0.007200643)  
##  
## lambda: 0.5288375  
## bootstrap mean: 0.3128604 (on raw scale)  
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.7040585)  
##  
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
NEOphydat2 %>% drop_na(PC2relegg) %>% summarize(mean = mean(PC2relegg)) #Figure S2
```

```
## mean
```

```
## 1 1.163413
```

```
#Asymmetry
```

```
modP3 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg + IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat2, n
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg + IncSite, :  
## will drop from the tree 821 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modP3) #Table S22
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg +  
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat2, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)
```

```
##
```

```
## AIC logLik
```

```
## 254.8 -118.4
```

```
##
```

```
## Raw residuals:
```

```
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
```

```
## -2.5557 -0.2215 0.1970 0.5724 2.7064
```

```
##
```

```
## Mean tip height: 59.8139
```

```
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
```

```
## lambda : 0.8781061
```

```
## sigma2: 0.02080124
```

```
##
```

```
## Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	StdErr	t.value	lowerbootCI	upperbootCI	p.value
## (Intercept)	0.499223	0.580212	0.860415	-0.444562	1.3714	0.391558
## sPC1mass	0.231115	0.208419	1.108895	-0.222470	0.6359	0.270058
## sPC2relegg	0.091764	0.143746	0.638374	-0.196720	0.3493	0.524647
## sHWI	0.646533	0.220718	2.929223	0.277319	1.1127	0.004184 **
## sCSegeg	0.735361	0.284617	2.583684	0.195602	1.2904	0.011178 *
## IncSitePL	-0.251591	0.475682	-0.528905	-1.164629	0.5799	0.598010
## IncSiteSC	0.691021	0.411194	1.680522	-0.031862	1.3036	0.095886 .

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
##
```

```
## R-squared: 0.2152 Adjusted R-squared: 0.1694
```

```
##
```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8781061.
```

```
##
```

```
## sigma2: 0.02080124
```

```
## bootstrap mean: 0.01898646 (on raw scale)
```

```
## 0.01851704 (on log scale, then back transformed)
```

```
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.01209613,0.02663014)
```

```
##
```

```
## lambda: 0.8781061
```

```
## bootstrap mean: 0.8388496 (on raw scale)
```

```
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6609292,0.9687006)
```

```
##
```

```
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```

###Coraciiformes
NEOphydat3 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Coraciiformes") %>% droplevels()
#Asymmetry
modP4 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSegeg +IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data =NEOphydat3, m

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg + IncSite, :
## will drop from the tree 903 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg + IncSite, : the estimation of lambda
##
## You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".

summary(modP4) #Table S22, Figure 7

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegeg +
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat3, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
## boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 51.79 -17.89
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -0.62197 -0.33896 -0.03482 0.23038 1.66607
##
## Mean tip height: 62.99596
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.003336459
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.924983 0.246932 -3.745902 -1.297291 -0.4042 0.001119 **
## sPC1mass 0.273582 0.232956 1.174394 -0.042977 0.6453 0.252793
## sPC2relegg -0.051195 0.283309 -0.180705 -0.577463 0.3990 0.858254
## sHWI -0.363729 0.237246 -1.533128 -0.781859 0.0389 0.139500
## sCSegeg -0.135829 0.280615 -0.484041 -0.579233 0.2456 0.633140
## IncSiteCV 0.387563 0.274604 1.411349 -0.032966 0.8530 0.172128
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.2904 Adjusted R-squared: 0.1292
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.003336459
## bootstrap mean: 0.002590942 (on raw scale)
## 0.00246135 (on log scale, then back transformed)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.001402848,0.004859705)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
## bootstrap mean: 0.06919249 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.8992484)
##

```

```
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
###Galliformes
NEOphydat4 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Galliformes") %>% droplevels()
#Asymmetry
modP5 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSegg + IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat4
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg + IncSite, :
## will drop from the tree 858 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg + IncSite, : the estimation of lambda
## You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
```

```
summary(modP5) #Table S22, Figure 7
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSegg +
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat4, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
## boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 117.63 -49.81
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -0.94219 -0.31024 -0.00733  0.30222  1.20340
##
## Mean tip height: 63.25872
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.00362327
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept) -0.390914  0.275511 -1.418866  -0.942492    0.1492  0.160643
## sPC1mass     -0.160025  0.145510 -1.099751  -0.448241    0.1644  0.275436
## sPC2relegg   -0.092551  0.089331 -1.036050  -0.277560    0.0865  0.303960
## sHWI          0.360017  0.147754  2.436602   0.108352    0.6365  0.017531 *
## sCSegg        0.233558  0.070119  3.330887   0.137205    0.3540  0.001421 **
## IncSitePL     0.208798  0.284158  0.734793  -0.326177    0.7913  0.465068
## IncSiteSC     1.062167  0.410293  2.588798   0.344501    1.7928  0.011836 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.7652    Adjusted R-squared: 0.7439
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.00362327
##      bootstrap mean: 0.003270985 (on raw scale)
##                   0.003230197 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.002392085,0.004390716)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##      bootstrap mean: 1e-07 (on raw scale)
```

```

##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1e-07)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
nobs(modP5)

## [1] 73
###Procellariiformes
NEOphydat5 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Procellariiformes") %>% droplevels()
modP8 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg +sHWI +IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat5, model = "lambda", boot = 100)

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sHWI + IncSite, phy = NEOphy, :
## will drop from the tree 904 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sHWI + IncSite, phy = NEOphy, : the estimation of lambda
##      You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
summary(modP8) #Table S18a

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sHWI + IncSite,
##      data = NEOphydat5, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 34.658 -9.329
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -0.87453 -0.03833  0.02926  0.19123  0.70729
##
## Mean tip height: 63.24302
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.001847686
##
## Coefficients:
##      Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept) -1.50330  0.55964 -2.68620   -2.38930   -0.6674  0.01383 *
## PC1mass      0.99287  0.17561  5.65381    0.65824    1.2854 1.303e-05 ***
## PC2relegg    0.65745  0.23374  2.81269    0.24527    1.1307  0.01043 *
## sHWI         0.21197  0.26686  0.79432   -0.11399    0.6680  0.43590
## IncSitePL    0.43549  0.28103  1.54961   -0.12640    0.8285  0.13617
## IncSiteSC   -0.57269  0.48962 -1.16966   -1.50881    0.3824  0.25524
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.8476      Adjusted R-squared: 0.8114
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.001847686
##      bootstrap mean: 0.00146649 (on raw scale)
##                      0.001378325 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.0006990703,0.00263195)
##

```

```

## lambda: 1e-07
##      bootstrap mean: 0.02729132 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.4031819)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
NEOphydat3 %>% drop_na(PC2relegg) %>% summarize(mean = mean(PC2relegg)) #Figure S2

##      mean
## 1 0.5568084

###Strigiformes
NEOphydat6 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Strigiformes") %>% droplevels()
#Asymmetry
modP9 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSeg +IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat6,

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg + IncSite, :
## will drop from the tree 905 taxa with missing data
summary(modP9) #Table S22,

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg +
##      IncSite, data = NEOphydat6, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##      boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 41.12 -10.56
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -0.50110 -0.25386 -0.16163  0.06362  1.14861
##
## Mean tip height: 75.80674
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.6597238
## sigma2: 0.002644932
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.736897  0.681295 -1.081612  -2.013957    0.4433  0.2937
## sPC1mass    -0.038959  0.281940 -0.138183  -0.411315    0.5118  0.8916
## sPC2relegg  0.068790  0.113186  0.607763  -0.072539    0.2864  0.5509
## sHWI        0.280100  0.353226  0.792976  -0.303188    0.7854  0.4381
## sCSeg       -0.025277  0.217725 -0.116097  -0.327563    0.3681  0.9089
## IncSiteCV   -0.315829  0.575745 -0.548557  -1.313632    0.8705  0.5900
## IncSitePL   -0.316638  0.645854 -0.490262  -1.448706    0.9296  0.6299
## IncSiteSC   0.107610  0.878660  0.122471  -1.250489    1.6076  0.9039
##
## R-squared: 0.09927   Adjusted R-squared: -0.251
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.6597238.
##
## sigma2: 0.002644932
##      bootstrap mean: 0.001438257 (on raw scale)

```

```
##          0.001178113 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.0004914611,0.004382979)
##
## lambda: 0.6597238
##      bootstrap mean: 0.1995469 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
###Tinamiformes
```

```
PALEOphydat1 <- PALEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Tinamiformes") %>% droplevels()
modP10<- phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg +sCSegg +sHWI, phy = PALEOphy, data = PALEOphydat1, model =
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI, phy =
## PALEOphy, : will drop from the tree 8 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI, phy = PALEOphy, : the estimation of
##          You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
```

```
summary(modP10) #Figure 4b, Table S19
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI,
##      data = PALEOphydat1, phy = PALEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 25.602 -5.801
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.2294 -0.1168  0.2939  0.3214  0.5262
##
## Mean tip height: 69.86872
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.004396107
##
## Coefficients:
##          Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.86953  1.12465 -0.77316   -2.12984    0.0394  0.5203
## PC1mass      0.63062  3.03308  0.20791   -1.91504    3.8129  0.8545
## PC2relegg    1.47948  1.50983  0.97989   -0.06395    3.4219  0.4305
## sCSegg       0.71066  1.28019  0.55512   -0.65969    1.9872  0.6346
## sHWI         1.79842  1.61974  1.11032    0.10451    3.6364  0.3825
##
## R-squared: 0.517 Adjusted R-squared: -0.4491
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.004396107
##      bootstrap mean: 0.001217246 (on raw scale)
##          0.0007306277 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (2.868155e-05,0.003476228)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
```

```
## bootstrap mean: 1e-07 (on raw scale)
## bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1e-07)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

13.1.1 Passeriformes Table S18, S20; Figures 6b, S2

```
####descriptive stats for relative egg size
NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Passeriformes") %>% summarise(Mean = MeanCI(PC2relegg, na.rm = TRUE)) #F
```

```
## Mean
## 1 -0.2337479
## 2 -0.2917953
## 3 -0.1757004
```

```
#Elongation
NEOphydat10 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(Order == "Passeriformes") %>% droplevels()
modQ1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSeg +IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat10,
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg + IncSite, :
## will drop from the tree 574 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg + IncSite, : 2
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modQ1) #Table S18b, S20
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg +
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat10, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
## boot = 100)
##
## AIC logLik
## 587.7 -282.9
##
## Raw residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -1.6329 -0.1899 0.1190 0.5157 1.7413
##
## Mean tip height: 70.52419
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.4226951
## sigma2: 0.00519187
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) 0.207625 0.323894 0.641026 -0.293449 0.8299 0.5219274
## sPC1mass 0.328747 0.089436 3.675765 0.155378 0.5311 0.0002745 ***
## sPC2relegg -0.036524 0.060554 -0.603171 -0.149064 0.0704 0.5467878
## sHWI 0.131594 0.068522 1.920470 -0.012934 0.2462 0.0556155 .
## sCSeg -0.256119 0.068484 -3.739844 -0.415707 -0.1310 0.0002152 ***
## IncSiteCU -0.138308 0.278301 -0.496972 -0.708408 0.2776 0.6195223
## IncSiteCV -0.344124 0.288739 -1.191816 -0.880268 0.1606 0.2341455
## IncSiteDO 0.064270 0.284921 0.225572 -0.446235 0.4830 0.8216666
## IncSitePL 0.119943 0.328167 0.365494 -0.472086 0.6128 0.7149650
```

```

## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.1338    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1138
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.4226951.
##
## sigma2: 0.00519187
##      bootstrap mean: 0.0048266 (on raw scale)
##                   0.004783127 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.00361678,0.006189995)
##
## lambda: 0.4226951
##      bootstrap mean: 0.3516659 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.5791545)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
#Asymmetry
#AS for cup nests only and CS less than or equal to 6
NEOphydat11 <- NEOphydat10 %>% filter(CSsegg <= 6) %>% droplevels()
modQ2<- phylolm(RC1AS~PC1mass +PC2relegg +sCSsegg +sHWI +IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat11, mod
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSsegg + sHWI + IncSite, : will
## drop from the tree 586 taxa with missing data
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSsegg + sHWI + IncSite, : 2
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
summary(modQ2) #Table S20, Figure S7 <support for Fig 6b>
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + sCSsegg + sHWI +
##      IncSite, data = NEOphydat11, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##      boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
##      532   -255
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -1.82622 -0.36226 -0.06245  0.30516  1.47181
##
## Mean tip height: 70.52419
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.4236344
## sigma2: 0.004671932
##
## Coefficients:
##      Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI    p.value
## (Intercept)  0.0850436  0.3081153  0.2760122  -0.5026805    0.6282  0.78271
## PC1mass     -0.0451059  0.0856415 -0.5266823  -0.1627031    0.1191  0.59876
## PC2relegg   -0.0024961  0.0589235 -0.0423624  -0.1240958    0.1277  0.96623
## sCSsegg     0.1313730  0.0778857  1.6867405  -0.0137838    0.2781  0.09258
## sHWI        0.2928476  0.0669781  4.3722872   0.1600034    0.4182 1.642e-05

```

```
## IncSiteCU    0.3786330  0.2653234  1.4270621  -0.0637171    0.8433  0.15449
## IncSiteCV    0.1939658  0.2820413  0.6877211  -0.3133997    0.7332  0.49210
## IncSiteDO    0.2707794  0.2715642  0.9971098  -0.2715910    0.7671  0.31943
## IncSitePL    0.3320110  0.3116932  1.0651853  -0.2281459    0.8497  0.28756
##
## (Intercept)
## PC1mass
## PC2relegg
## sCSegg      .
## sHWI        ***
## IncSiteCU
## IncSiteCV
## IncSiteDO
## IncSitePL
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
##
## R-squared:  0.09971   Adjusted R-squared:  0.07828
##
```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.4236344.
```

```
##
## sigma2: 0.004671932
##   bootstrap mean: 0.004300588 (on raw scale)
##                   0.004272582 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003389951,0.005260374)
##
```

```
## lambda: 0.4236344
##   bootstrap mean: 0.3364876 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.5725751)
##
```

```
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
#plot predicted regressions for the whole order
modPLQ2 <- lm(RC1AS~PC1mass +PC2relegg +CSegg +HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Order == "Passeriformes" & IncSite == "CU" & CSegg <= 6))
summary(modPLQ2)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, data = subset(NEOphydat, Order == "Passeriformes" & IncSite == "CU" & CSegg <= 6))
##
```

```
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.69869 -0.32012  0.01632  0.35612  1.22610
##
```

```
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.207287   0.131468  -1.577  0.11624
## PC1mass     -0.074192   0.100620  -0.737  0.46166
## PC2relegg    0.009050   0.074125   0.122  0.90293
## CSegg        0.014611   0.039824   0.367  0.71403
## HWI          0.015666   0.004975   3.149  0.00185 **
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
##
```

```
## Residual standard error: 0.5389 on 230 degrees of freedom
## (2 observations deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared: 0.06737, Adjusted R-squared: 0.05115
## F-statistic: 4.154 on 4 and 230 DF, p-value: 0.002873
```

```
nobs(modPLQ2)
```

```
## [1] 235
```

```
plot_model(modPLQ2, type = "pred", terms = "CSeegg") #<Figure 6b all species with cup nests>
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
#plot predicted regressions for each family with greater than 5 species that have cup nests and less th
modQ2a <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSeegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Acrocephalidae" & IncS
nobs(modQ2a)
```

```
## [1] 10
```

```
plot_model(modQ2a, type = "pred", terms = "CSeegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2b <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Alaudidae" & IncSite ==  
nobs(modQ2b)
```

```
## [1] 13
```

```
plot_model(modQ2b, type = "pred")
```

```
## $PC1mass
```



```
##  
## $PC2relegg
```

Predicted values of RC1AS

##

\$CSegg

Predicted values of RC1AS

\$HWI

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2c <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Campephagidae" & IncSi  
nobs(modQ2c)
```

```
## [1] 8
```

```
plot_model(modQ2c, type = "pred")
```

```
## $PC1mass
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
##  
## $PC2relegg
```

Predicted values of RC1AS

##

\$CSegg

Predicted values of RC1AS

\$HWI

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2f <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Emberizidae" & IncSi  
nobs(modQ2f)
```

```
## [1] 6
```

```
plot_model(modQ2f, type = "pred")
```

```
## $PC1mass
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
##  
## $PC2relegg
```

Predicted values of RC1AS

##

\$CSegg

\$HWI

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2g <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Fringillidae" & IncSit  
nobs(modQ2g)
```

```
## [1] 13
```

```
plot_model(modQ2g, type = "pred")
```

```
## $PC1mass
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
##  
## $PC2relegg
```

Predicted values of RC1AS

##

\$CSeegg

Predicted values of RC1AS

\$HWI

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2i <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Leiothrichidae" & Inc  
nobs(modQ2i)
```

```
## [1] 6
```

```
plot_model(modQ2i, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2j <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Meliphagidae" & IncSi  
nobs(modQ2j)
```

```
## [1] 8
```

```
plot_model(modQ2j, type = "pred", terms="CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ21 <- lm(RC1AS~PC1mass +PC2relegg +CSegg +HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Motacillidae" & IncSi  
nobs(modQ21)
```

```
## [1] 13
```

```
plot_model(modQ21, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2m <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Muscicapidae" & IncSi  
nobs(modQ2m)
```

```
## [1] 33
```

```
plot_model(modQ2m, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2n <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Paradisaeidae" & IncS  
nobs(modQ2n)
```

```
## [1] 9
```

```
plot_model(modQ2n, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2r <- lm(RC1AS~PC1mass +PC2relegg +CSegg +HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Pycnonotidae" & IncSi  
nobs(modQ2r)
```

```
## [1] 10
```

```
plot_model(modQ2r, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2t <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Sylviidae" & IncSite == "1"))
nobs(modQ2t)
```

```
## [1] 12
```

```
plot_model(modQ2t, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2u <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Turdidae" & IncSite == "u"))
nobs(modQ2u)
```

```
## [1] 9
```

```
plot_model(modQ2u, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS


```
modQ2v <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg + CSegg + HWI, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Tyrannidae" & IncSite  
nobs(modQ2v)
```

```
## [1] 6
```

```
plot_model(modQ2v, type = "pred", terms = "CSegg")
```

Predicted values of RC1AS

13.2 Within families of Galliformes

Table S11

```
#Phasianidae
modR1 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg, phy = NEOphy, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Phasianidae"),
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg, phy = NEOphy,
## subset(NEOphydat, : will drop from the tree 897 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modR1) #Table S11
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg, data = subset(NEOphydat,
##   Family == "Phasianidae"), phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##   boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 60.37 -25.18
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.33170 -0.44159  0.02605  0.47464  0.93393
##
## Mean tip height: 19.0391
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1
```

```

## sigma2: 0.02491516
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.57461  0.32849 -1.74923   -1.22221   -0.0472  0.09015 .
## sPC1mass     0.65526  0.24590  2.66477    0.32012    1.0556  0.01212 *
## sPC2relegg   0.13753  0.14352  0.95824   -0.15000    0.3872  0.34536
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.1913   Adjusted R-squared:  0.1391
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1.
##
## sigma2: 0.02491516
##      bootstrap mean: 0.02196719 (on raw scale)
##                   0.02106859 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.01038143,0.03297078)
##
## lambda: 1
##      bootstrap mean: 0.9662189 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.6539973,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
NEOphydat %>% filter(Family == "Phasianidae") %>% summarize(mean = mean(PC2relegg)) #Figure S2

##           mean
## 1 -1.142509

#Cracidae
modR2 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg, phy = NEOphy, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Cracidae"), model = "lambda", boot = 100)

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = NEOphy,
## subset(NEOphydat, : will drop from the tree 911 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = NEOphy, subset(NEOphydat, : the estimation of
##                               You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".

summary(modR2) #Table S11

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = subset(NEOphydat,
##           Family == "Cracidae"), phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 40.41 -15.20
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.2232 -0.2099 -0.1146  0.1397  1.2709
##
## Mean tip height: 14.352
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.01866091

```

```

##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate   StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) 0.131526 0.570940 0.230367 -0.711295    0.9864 0.8206
## PC1mass     0.067889 0.388527 0.174733 -0.491558    0.5621 0.8634
## PC2relegg   0.313781 0.249461 1.257834 -0.108071    0.7623 0.2255
##
## R-squared: 0.08627   Adjusted R-squared: -0.02123
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.01866091
##   bootstrap mean: 0.01544913 (on raw scale)
##                   0.01448786 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.007335878,0.02844141)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##   bootstrap mean: 0.02217679 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.2368711)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
NEOphydat %>% filter(Family == "Cracidae") %>% drop_na(PC2relegg) %>% summarize(mean = mean(PC2relegg))
##           mean
## 1 0.6842882
#Megapodiidae
modR3 <- phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = NEOphy, subset(NEOphydat, Family == "Megapodiidae"))
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = NEOphy,
## subset(NEOphydat, : will drop from the tree 917 taxa with missing data
## Warning in phylolm(RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, phy = NEOphy, subset(NEOphydat, : the estimation of
## You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
summary(modR3) #Table S11
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC2EL ~ PC1mass + PC2relegg, data = subset(NEOphydat,
##   Family == "Megapodiidae"), phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##   boot = 100)
##
##   AIC logLik
## 25.866 -7.933
##
## Raw residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -0.5782 -0.2999 -0.1466  0.3058  0.9173
##
## Mean tip height: 51.00721
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.003565191
##
## Coefficients:

```

```
##           Estimate   StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) 0.891925 1.352622 0.659405 -1.457459 3.4430 0.52320
## PC1mass     -0.030406 0.633720 -0.047979 -1.090091 1.3501 0.96259
## PC2relegg   0.568267 0.299022 1.900419 0.058244 1.0665 0.08389 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.3674    Adjusted R-squared: 0.2524
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.003565191
##   bootstrap mean: 0.002863436 (on raw scale)
##                   0.002605405 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.0008934118,0.005375729)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##   bootstrap mean: 0.1239786 (on raw scale)
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
NEOphydat %>% filter(Family == "Megapodiidae") %>% drop_na(PC2relegg) %>% summarize(mean = mean(PC2relegg))
```

```
##           mean
## 1 2.253903
```

14 CLUTCH SIZE: effects on asymmetry

Table S21, Figure 6a

```
dev.off()
```

```
## null device
##           1
```

```
#model for neognath species not using scrapes
```

```
NEOphyns <- NEOphydat %>% filter(!IncSite == "SC") %>% droplevels()
modS1 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSeg + sHWI + LOCO + IncSite, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphyns)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSeg + sHWI + LOCO + : will
## drop from the tree 124 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSeg + sHWI + LOCO + : 4
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modS1) #Table S21
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSeg + sHWI +
##         LOCO + IncSite, data = NEOphyns, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##         boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 1387.9 -677.9
##
```

```

## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.7781 -0.0451  0.6076  1.1258  3.6375
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.6930888
## sigma2: 0.005796946
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate      StdErr    t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value
## (Intercept) -0.9289426  0.3210236 -2.8936897  -1.4185882   -0.4243  0.003912
## sPC1mass     0.0584752  0.0532727  1.0976574  -0.0422806    0.1716  0.272687
## sPC2relegg  -0.0521396  0.0342570 -1.5220143  -0.1049969    0.0294  0.128404
## sCSegg       0.0683635  0.0358026  1.9094578   0.0045791    0.1364  0.056564
## sHWI         0.2663137  0.0469540  5.6718009   0.2009146    0.3543  1.98e-08
## LOCOC        0.4525192  0.1970513  2.2964542   0.1161780    0.8456  0.021910
## LOCOP        1.4390834  0.5172033  2.7824326   0.6506677    2.4418  0.005524
## LOCOP        0.1159257  0.2082296  0.5567205  -0.2569483    0.5768  0.577875
## LOCOS        0.2649072  0.2091064  1.2668539  -0.1382817    0.6385  0.205579
## IncSiteCU    0.2470807  0.1567893  1.5758774  -0.0198308    0.5227  0.115453
## IncSiteCV    0.2101329  0.1461493  1.4377968  -0.0187252    0.4494  0.150886
## IncSiteDO    0.2556787  0.1739948  1.4694618  -0.0613413    0.5942  0.142104
## IncSiteMO   -0.4859838  0.4584829 -1.0599823  -1.4471704    0.2657  0.289475
## IncSitePL    0.0624208  0.1551813  0.4022447  -0.1625272    0.3378  0.687612
##
## (Intercept) **
## sPC1mass
## sPC2relegg
## sCSegg      .
## sHWI        ***
## LOCOC       *
## LOCOP       **
## LOCOS
## IncSiteCU
## IncSiteCV
## IncSiteDO
## IncSiteMO
## IncSitePL
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.07186   Adjusted R-squared: 0.05665
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.6930888.
##
## sigma2: 0.005796946
##      bootstrap mean: 0.005554048 (on raw scale)
##                   0.005528688 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.004696167,0.006671761)
##
## lambda: 0.6930888
##      bootstrap mean: 0.6727633 (on raw scale)

```

```

##          bootstrap 95% CI: (0.5764433,0.7470912)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
#plot for all species not using scrapes; variables not standardized
modS1a <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg +CSegg +HWI +LOCO +IncSite, data = NEOphyns)
nobs(modS1a)

## [1] 811
visreg(modS1a, xvar = "CSegg") #Figure 6a

####model for neognath species using scrapes with clutch size less than or equal to 4
NEOphySC <- NEOphydat%>% filter(IncSite == "SC" & CSegg <=4) %>% droplevels()
modS2 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sCSegg +sHWI +LOCO, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphySC, model

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI + LOCO, : will
## drop from the tree 824 taxa with missing data

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI + LOCO, : 1
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored

summary(modS2) #Table S21

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI +
##         LOCO, data = NEOphySC, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 237.8 -109.9
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.9421 -0.3515  1.1036  1.8391  3.7607
##
## Mean tip height: 87.08247
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.8873304
## sigma2: 0.01160344
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI   p.value
## (Intercept)  0.471891  0.474188  0.995156  -0.402228    1.2761    0.3221
## sPC1mass     0.236493  0.201484  1.173759  -0.224596    0.6467    0.2433
## sPC2relegg   0.152065  0.109084  1.394013  -0.074531    0.4120    0.1664
## sCSegg       1.285178  0.255527  5.029525   0.801453    1.7621 2.167e-06 ***
## sHWI         0.258187  0.156873  1.645841  -0.018552    0.6171    0.1029
## LOCOC       -0.560405  0.395849 -1.415705  -1.360564    0.2316    0.1600
## LOCOS        0.549584  0.521755  1.053338  -0.512618    1.3531    0.2947
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared: 0.2668      Adjusted R-squared: 0.2228
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8873304.
##

```

```
## sigma2: 0.01160344
##      bootstrap mean: 0.01002728 (on raw scale)
##              0.009695787 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.005779725,0.01559568)
##
## lambda: 0.8873304
##      bootstrap mean: 0.8342792 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.5722897,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modS2)
```

```
## [1] 107
```

```
#plot for species using scrapes; variables not standardized
modS2a <- lm(RC1AS ~ PC1mass +PC2relegg +CSegg +HWI +LOCO, data = NEOphySC) #Figure 6a
nobs(modS2a)
```

```
## [1] 108
```

```
visreg(modS2a, xvar = "CSegg") #Figure 6a
```

```
####model for neognath species using scrapes with clutch size greater than 4
NEOphydat11 <- NEOphydat %>% filter(IncSite == "SC" & CSegg >4) %>% droplevels()
modS3 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sCSegg +sHWI, phy = NEOphy, data = NEOphydat11, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI, phy =
## NEOphy, : will drop from the tree 924 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI, phy = NEOphy, : the estimation of
## lambda is unreliable. You may change the bounds using options "upper.bound" and "lower.bound".
```

```
summary(modS3)
```

```
##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sCSegg + sHWI,
## data = NEOphydat11, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
##
##      AIC  logLik
## 14.9354 -0.4677
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -0.32296 -0.23785  0.06374  0.14806  0.43881
##
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 1e-07
## sigma2: 0.0006483085
##
## Coefficients:
##      Estimate  StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept)  2.95738  2.21686  1.33404    0.94640    5.7195  0.3138
## sPC1mass     -3.69785  2.13034 -1.73580   -6.25755   -1.9010  0.2247
## sPC2relegg   -0.33203  0.41766 -0.79497   -0.90276    0.1010  0.5100
## sCSegg       -0.71252  0.78703 -0.90532   -1.69506    0.0011  0.4609
```

```
## sHWI      -2.74780  1.61761 -1.69868   -4.62998   -1.1634  0.2315
##
## R-squared: 0.9398    Adjusted R-squared: 0.8193
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=1e-07.
##
## sigma2: 0.0006483085
##      bootstrap mean: 0.0001849359 (on raw scale)
##                  9.467771e-05 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (5.991755e-06,0.0007031418)
##
## lambda: 1e-07
##      bootstrap mean: 0.1600001 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,1)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modS3)
```

```
## [1] 7
```

```
modS3a <- lm(RC1AS ~ sCSege, subset(ALLphydat, IncSite == "SC" & CSege >4)) #Table S21, all are perching
summary(modS3a)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = RC1AS ~ sCSege, data = subset(ALLphydat, IncSite ==
##      "SC" & CSege > 4))
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.6930 -0.8716 -0.4246  0.9784  2.5292
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.9033     0.4952  -1.824  0.0869 .
## sCSege        0.1329     0.1526   0.871  0.3965
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.345 on 16 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.0453, Adjusted R-squared:  -0.01437
## F-statistic: 0.7592 on 1 and 16 DF,  p-value: 0.3965
```

```
nobs(modS3a)
```

```
## [1] 18
```

15 MODELS TO PREDICT ASYMMETRY FOR EACH MODE OF LOCOMOTION

Table S17

```
#aerial
NEOphydat12a <- NEOphydat %>% filter(LOCO == "A") %>% droplevels()
modT1 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSege +IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = NEOphydat12a, r
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSege + IncSite, :  
## will drop from the tree 780 taxa with missing data
```

```
summary(modT1) #Table S17
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSege +  
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat12a, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)  
##  
## AIC logLik  
## 271.3 -123.6  
##  
## Raw residuals:  
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -1.33538 -0.44500 -0.05029 0.96245 2.81510  
##  
## Mean tip height: 81.93629  
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:  
## lambda : 0.7090723  
## sigma2: 0.006485239  
##  
## Coefficients:  
## Estimate StdErr t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value  
## (Intercept) -0.106251 0.321481 -0.330504 -0.758786 0.4215 0.741510  
## sPC1mass 0.342553 0.129428 2.646663 0.095551 0.5957 0.009053 **  
## sPC2relegg -0.018037 0.079379 -0.227226 -0.144752 0.1396 0.820577  
## sHWI 0.004460 0.124234 0.035900 -0.185410 0.2400 0.971413  
## sCSege 0.342670 0.175833 1.948844 0.063591 0.5976 0.053300 .  
## IncSiteCU -0.205169 0.560118 -0.366296 -1.000835 0.7084 0.714693  
## IncSiteCV -0.066491 0.345074 -0.192686 -0.688545 0.5936 0.847483  
## IncSiteDO 0.082314 0.652706 0.126112 -1.178508 1.5548 0.899823  
## IncSitePL -0.336528 0.311493 -1.080368 -0.999259 0.1478 0.281823  
## IncSiteSC 0.045638 0.329183 0.138642 -0.664585 0.6818 0.889931  
## ---  
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1  
##  
## R-squared: 0.1118 Adjusted R-squared: 0.05511  
##  
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7090723.  
##  
## sigma2: 0.006485239  
## bootstrap mean: 0.005346993 (on raw scale)  
## 0.005197914 (on log scale, then back transformed)  
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003252796,0.007780058)  
##  
## lambda: 0.7090723  
## bootstrap mean: 0.6027548 (on raw scale)  
## bootstrap 95% CI: (0.1071341,0.8174753)  
##  
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modT1)
```

```
## [1] 151
```

```
#cursorial
```

```
NEOphydat12c <- NEOphydat %>% filter(LOCO == "C") %>% droplevels()
```

```
modT2 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeegg + IncSite, phy=NEOphy, NEOphydat12c, model
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeegg + IncSite, :  
## will drop from the tree 720 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeegg + IncSite, : 1  
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modT2) #Table S17
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeegg +  
## IncSite, data = NEOphydat12c, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",  
## boot = 100)
```

```
##
```

```
## AIC logLik
```

```
## 440.9 -207.5
```

```
##
```

```
## Raw residuals:
```

```
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -2.5917 -0.1540 0.3284 1.2012 3.8478
```

```
##
```

```
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
```

```
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
```

```
## lambda : 0.8741423
```

```
## sigma2: 0.01035301
```

```
##
```

```
## Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	StdErr	t.value	lowerbootCI	upperbootCI	p.value
## (Intercept)	0.4553408	1.0516747	0.4329674	-1.4783306	2.2646	0.6655
## sPC1mass	-0.0253617	0.1236985	-0.2050283	-0.2351915	0.1358	0.8378
## sPC2relegg	0.0204101	0.0718121	0.2842149	-0.0845744	0.1768	0.7765
## sHWI	0.4735051	0.0993591	4.7655933	0.3095771	0.6436	3.616e-06
## sCSeegg	0.2807365	0.0607060	4.6245309	0.1736220	0.3984	6.732e-06
## IncSiteCU	-0.5001978	1.1801697	-0.4238355	-2.7504038	1.4943	0.6721
## IncSiteCV	-0.0115745	1.1610934	-0.0099687	-1.8438529	2.4131	0.9921
## IncSiteD0	-1.0850674	1.3316464	-0.8148315	-3.6141157	1.2694	0.4161
## IncSiteM0	-1.3539115	1.2070242	-1.1216938	-3.5662012	0.7204	0.2633
## IncSitePL	-0.9215074	1.0072603	-0.9148652	-2.6657860	0.8595	0.3614
## IncSiteSC	-0.4979588	1.0277439	-0.4845164	-2.3031797	1.1300	0.6285

```
##
```

```
## (Intercept)
```

```
## sPC1mass
```

```
## sPC2relegg
```

```
## sHWI ***
```

```
## sCSeegg ***
```

```
## IncSiteCU
```

```
## IncSiteCV
```

```
## IncSiteD0
```

```

## IncSiteM0
## IncSitePL
## IncSiteSC
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.2503    Adjusted R-squared:  0.2128
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.8741423.
##
## sigma2: 0.01035301
##      bootstrap mean: 0.009273538 (on raw scale)
##                   0.009146789 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.006997188,0.01295487)
##
## lambda: 0.8741423
##      bootstrap mean: 0.8450994 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.7242397,0.9478795)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modT2)
```

```
## [1] 211
```

```
#perching
```

```

NEOphydat12p <- NEOphydat %>% filter(LOCO == "P") %>% droplevels()
modT3 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSeg +IncSite, phy=NEOphy, data = NEOphydat12p,

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg + IncSite, :
## will drop from the tree 471 taxa with missing data

```

```

## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg + IncSite, : 3
## taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored

```

```
summary(modT3) #Table S17
```

```

##
## Call:
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg +
##      IncSite, data = NEOphydat12p, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda",
##      boot = 100)
##
##      AIC logLik
## 731.1 -353.6
##
## Raw residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -1.0399  0.1814  0.6691  1.0385  2.1646
##
## Mean tip height: 87.08247
## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.5971989
## sigma2: 0.004869675
##
## Coefficients:
##      Estimate      StdErr  t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI  p.value

```

```
## (Intercept) -0.795087  0.237586 -3.346518   -1.130103   -0.4043  0.000887 ***
## sPC1mass    -0.059070  0.067478 -0.875392   -0.166753    0.0765  0.381828
## sPC2relegg  -0.035108  0.043936 -0.799076   -0.125520    0.0538  0.424668
## sHWI        0.268900  0.057887  4.645284    0.171038    0.3963  4.465e-06 ***
## sCSeg      0.017210  0.048464  0.355111   -0.065743    0.1097  0.722673
## IncSiteCU   0.367365  0.183910  1.997523    0.080811    0.6332  0.046370 *
## IncSiteCV   0.266196  0.172179  1.546040   -0.014892    0.5310  0.122798
## IncSiteD0   0.327075  0.195654  1.671706   -0.001633    0.6041  0.095277 .
## IncSitePL   0.171134  0.223327  0.766292   -0.262868    0.5578  0.443904
## IncSiteSC  -0.064450  0.662836 -0.097234   -1.168368    1.3181  0.922584
```

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
##
```

```
## R-squared:  0.06683   Adjusted R-squared:  0.04817
```

```
##
```

```
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.5971989.
```

```
##
```

```
## sigma2: 0.004869675
```

```
##   bootstrap mean: 0.004580174 (on raw scale)
```

```
##               0.004548284 (on log scale, then back transformed)
```

```
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003710013,0.00570444)
```

```
##
```

```
## lambda: 0.5971989
```

```
##   bootstrap mean: 0.5538816 (on raw scale)
```

```
##   bootstrap 95% CI: (0.4153564,0.7044579)
```

```
##
```

```
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates
```

```
nobs(modT3)
```

```
## [1] 460
```

```
#swimming
```

```
NEOphydat12s <- NEOphydat %>% filter(LOCO == "S") %>% droplevels()
```

```
modT4 <- phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass +sPC2relegg +sHWI +sCSeg, phy=NEOphy, data=NEOphydat12s, model ="lambda")
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg, phy =
```

```
## NEOphy, : will drop from the tree 848 taxa with missing data
```

```
## Warning in phylolm(RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg, phy =
```

```
## NEOphy, : 1 taxa not in the tree: their data will be ignored
```

```
summary(modT4) #Table S17
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
```

```
## phylolm(formula = RC1AS ~ sPC1mass + sPC2relegg + sHWI + sCSeg,
```

```
##   data = NEOphydat12s, phy = NEOphy, model = "lambda", boot = 100)
```

```
##
```

```
##   AIC logLik
```

```
## 172.4 -79.2
```

```
##
```

```
## Raw residuals:
```

```
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
```

```
## -1.6597 -0.3035  0.1699  0.5573  1.9643
```

```
##
```

```
## Mean tip height: 103.2234
```

```

## Parameter estimate(s) using ML:
## lambda : 0.7855217
## sigma2: 0.01020314
##
## Coefficients:
##      Estimate      StdErr   t.value lowerbootCI upperbootCI p.value
## (Intercept) -0.750659  0.572477 -1.311248  -1.713437    0.2941  0.19362
## sPC1mass     0.406649  0.251288  1.618262  -0.191888    0.8329  0.10964
## sPC2relegg  -0.027812  0.141298 -0.196832  -0.398657    0.2454  0.84447
## sHWI         0.272841  0.192966  1.413933  -0.109415    0.6392  0.16136
## sCSeg       -0.260119  0.130548 -1.992513  -0.492432    0.0013  0.04981 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## R-squared:  0.1429      Adjusted R-squared:  0.09892
##
## Note: p-values and R-squared are conditional on lambda=0.7855217.
##
## sigma2: 0.01020314
##      bootstrap mean: 0.008251295 (on raw scale)
##                   0.007524222 (on log scale, then back transformed)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (0.003027835,0.01480652)
##
## lambda: 0.7855217
##      bootstrap mean: 0.650869 (on raw scale)
##      bootstrap 95% CI: (1e-07,0.900185)
##
## Parametric bootstrap results based on 100 fitted replicates

```

```
nobs(modT4)
```

```
## [1] 83
```